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WELCOME Software Design Strategy:

Key points towards an Integrated Care Software Platform

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WELCOME

Wearable Sensing and Smart Cloud Computing for Integrated Care to COPD Patients with Comorbidities

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Executive Summary

WELCOME is an ICT project aiming to develop an integrated care approach for monitoring, and treatment of patients suffering from Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) with comorbidities focusing on Chronic Heart Failure, Diabetes, Anxiety and Depression.

The WELCOME system includes a wearable vest and peripheral devices, which monitor the patient's biosignals, a communication hub (tablet) located in the patient's home, a cloud software stack and a variety of user applications, either through web or through a mobile interface. The WELCOME cloud infrastructure stores data transferred through the patient hub and uses a feature extraction server (FES) and a decision support system (DSS) to generate medically relevant information that can be used by the WELCOME applications. WELCOME applications help medical experts, informal carers and patients to continuously evaluate the patient's status while emphasizing on the integrated aspect of care.

Building upon the design work of the first two years, which has been reported in D3.1 and D3.2, D3.3 presents the overall system's design lifecycle and provides clarifications requested through the 2nd year's interim review's comments.

The overall design results have been reported in detail in the D3.1 and D3.2, and the purpose of this deliverable does not include the overall design outcome. The deliverable D3.3 has three main goals:

- a) To clarify crucial design issues of WELCOME software system, as suggested by reviewers, in order to complement the design presented in D3.1 and D3.2, with a link between the medical rationale and needs in their context and the WELCOME software design.
- b) To provide a clear view of the consortium's standards based design lifecycle, which could be exploited as part of a future plan for a marketable product
- c) To identify the steps needed towards a CE marking process

Regarding the document organization, the first section provides a brief introduction. In the second section, key design points are elaborated, as regards the users, the clinical pathways and characteristic workflows, the path to generate actionable data, and the data model strategy. Third section provides details regarding the followed design lifecycle namely its rationale and its main activities, focusing on WELCOME's not only academic or research oriented problems but also real world application's challenges. Fourth section describes the preparatory steps completed towards a possible future CE marking pathway, while also identifying issues left open. Finally, fifth section is a brief document conclusion. APPENDICES provide supplementary information linked with the main sections.

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1 Introduction

WELCOME develops an integrated care approach targeting on patients suffering from Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) with specific comorbidities (Chronic Heart Failure, Diabetes, Anxiety and Depression). The project focuses on using remote patient monitoring technologies and semi-automatic decision support techniques in order to facilitate early diagnosis and detection of exacerbations.

Figure 1: The general idea of the WELCOME project.

As depicted in Figure 1, the WELCOME system addresses the needs of patients, interacting with them via the patient hub and patient applications, and the various health professionals. Data management and processing takes place at a central cloud-based hub where a number of advanced processing services are hosted. The main pillars of the WELCOME solution for the patient and health professional are:

- Rich measurements collected through a wearable vest and a variety medical sensors (blood glucose, blood pressure, weight, and temperature and airflow obstruction from spirometry data) are collected via the patient hub, namely a tablet. Furthermore, the patient is provided with advanced Inhaler devices for measuring and evaluating their medical adherence and inhaling technique.
- A central data management and analysis space is hosted on cloud infrastructure, in order to extract high-level features of medical relevance out of the raw data signals. Furthermore, the Decision Support System (DSS) applies rules to the data and extracted high level features.

- User applications for all stakeholders are built (patients, informal carers and healthcare professionals). Applications are used to monitor patients' life style and overall health status through questionnaires and potential input from informal carers. Furthermore, WELCOME applications provide remote monitoring information and present alarming situations (e.g. alarms detected by the cloud DSS and based on cloud processing) to medical personnel.

In summary, Work Package 3 (WP3) deals with the overall system's design, having the basic requirements produced in Work Package 2 (WP2) as a prerequisite. The main input from WP2 came in the deliverables 2.1 and 2.2. The business processes and system requirements, as well as overall system architecture, and design decisions on the patient hub and the cloud system were defined during the first year, and reported in deliverable D3.1. This has set the basis for the initial developments of the cloud system (WP5) and user applications (WP6). During the 2nd year, WP3 continued incrementally building and refining design decisions for the WELCOME system, which were used for the complete system implementation in WP5-6-7. Updated system design was documented in D3.2, where we also included design changes to meet review comments, as well as parts that had been drafted during the first year and were better elaborated during the second year (e.g. the rules for the DSS, the orchestrator agent).

The deliverable D3.3, following the recommendations of reviewers (Recommendation 3 of the interim review consolidated report), is not documenting incremental updates. Instead, it is a deliverable presenting the WELCOME's strategy as concerns WELCOME software design.

Specifically, this deliverable starts with a description of the COPD users segmentation referring to the COPD stages and comorbid COPD, discusses on the segment targeted and links their care needs with the WELCOME system. As WELCOME addresses integrated care and comorbidity management, the way that the WELCOME business processes map to the diverse clinical workflows, along with the involved WELCOME user roles, are presented. Crucial for coordinated care, the HCP collaboration for COPD and comorbidity management is further discussed.

WELCOME system is data intensive and heavily investing on the added value offered for early diagnosis and management of COPD and comorbidities. Therefore WELCOME cloud data management and decision support are the parts that are further elaborated in this document. The path from sensor data to useful clinical information and knowledge, as envisioned and designed via the WP2-WP3 collaboration is addressed in Section 2.3. As regards the stability and maturity of the FHIR-based data management system, Section 2.5 refers to the strategy of HL7 FHIR adoption and the adoption of future updates. However, it is again noted that this document is not repeating software design information about the different parts of the system that have been reported before, e.g. the extensive documentation on feature extraction algorithms, nor is it repeating applications design that is reported in WP6 deliverables.

Finally, this document describes the rationale of the WELCOME software design lifecycle and risk management, and justifies how this process would facilitate a possible future product-building pathway through the adoption of specific standards and a map to a CE marking process. Section 3 describes the standards based rationale of the WELCOME software stack's design and risk management, namely following the IEC 62304 and ISO 14971 standards. Section 4 describes the preparatory steps as well as the open issues towards CE marking of WELCOME software. These sections depict the consortium's commitment to quality and the readiness to follow a product oriented pathway, even if this is considered out of the project's scope.

While this process has profound impact on WP3, WP5 and WP6, it is described in a deliverable of WP3, focusing on the design of the project.

2 Key WELCOME design points and clarifications

2.1 Mapping of COPD users, identification of target group and their requirements

Although the purpose of D3.3 is not to make a market analysis or an analysis of the WELCOME system impact, it was deemed necessary to include our view on the WELCOME users and their needs as investigated in WP2 and mapped to the system in WP3.

2.1.1 The COPD comorbid patients

COPD is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, especially among smokers over 40 years of age and individuals exposed to biomass smoke¹. The World Health Organization estimates that COPD will be the third most common worldwide cause of death and disability by 2030², from its current fifth ranking. The global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) grading system classifies COPD patients into four stages according to severity and disease progression ranging from mild to very severe. Typically, COPD patients who are classified as stage III or IV have more severe symptoms and are at higher risks of developing exacerbations as well as hospitalisation.

COPD comorbidities are quite frequent, including diseases that independently coexist with COPD with no other causation, diseases that share common risk factors and pathogenetic pathways with COPD. These comorbidities are often complicated by the interaction with the lung and systemic manifestations of COPD and vice versa. According to van Manen³ over 50% of patients with COPD had 1 to 2 comorbidities, 15.8% had 3 to 4 comorbidities, and 6.8% had 5 or more comorbid conditions. Concurrent comorbidities are known to markedly affect the health outcomes of COPD patients. A summary of the literature about the most common morbidities of COPD disease is presented next.

COPD and Depression/Anxiety: Depression and anxiety often co-occur; it is estimated that at least half of people with depression also have anxiety. Anxiety and depression are common entities in patients diagnosed with COPD⁴ and may lead to increased exacerbation, and hospitalisation as well as poorer disease outcomes. A study showed that about a quarter (24.6%) of COPD patients experienced clinically significant depressive symptoms compared with 11.7% of the controls. Clinical anxiety has also been recognized as a significant problem in COPD, with an estimated prevalence of up to 40%. Additionally, COPD patients are ten times more likely to experience panic disorder or panic attacks compared with general population samples. No differences in the prevalence of depression in COPD were found between studies of Western and non-Western populations. Disease severity does not

¹ G. Hillas, F. Perlikos, I. Tsiligianni, and N. Tzanakis, "Managing comorbidities in COPD," *International Journal of COPD*, vol. 10. pp. 95–109, 2015

² World Health Organization. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). 2011. Available from: <http://www.who.int/respiratory/copd> <http://www.who.int/respiratory/copd>. Accessed September 25, 2014.

³ J. G. van Manen, P. J. Bindels, C. J. IJzermans, J. S. van der Zee, B. J. Bottema, and E. Schadé, "Prevalence of comorbidity in patients with a chronic airway obstruction and controls over the age of 40.," *J. Clin. Epidemiol.*, vol. 54, no. 3, pp. 287–93, 2001.

⁴ Panagioti M, Scott C, Blakemore A, Coventry PA. Overview of the prevalence, impact, and management of depression and anxiety in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *International Journal of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease*. 2014;9:1289-1306. doi:10.2147/COPD.S72073.

appear to affect the levels of anxiety and depression in COPD patients. Subjective ratings of health-related quality of life (HRQoL), dyspnea, and reduced exercise capacity potentially underlie the development of symptoms of depression and anxiety in COPD. Depression and anxiety are more often reported in women than in men with COPD, but this is not independent of differences in perceived symptom control and severity of dyspnea symptoms.

The two main symptoms of major depression include depressed mood and loss of interest or pleasure in daily activities. Additional symptoms of depression include fatigue or loss of energy, significant changes in weight, appetite and sleep, guilt/worthlessness, lack of concentration, pessimism about the future, and suicidality.

COPD and Diabetes: Metabolic complications are common comorbidities of COPD, namely type 2 diabetes and metabolic syndrome. The prevalence of diabetes in COPD patients is 12.6–14.5% in an all-stage COPD population according to Mannino et al⁵. The prevalence of metabolic syndrome is 53% for GOLD grade 2 COPD, 37% for GOLD grade 3 COPD and 44% for GOLD grade 4 COPD according to Watz et al⁶. Moderate to severe COPD increases the risk of diabetes (OR 1.4 and 1.5, respectively), according to Mannino et al. It was found that 1.6 - 16% of COPD patients are diabetic, with prevalence increasing as lung function deteriorates⁷.

Systemic inflammation (with elevated markers such as CRP, TNF- α and IL-6) plays an important role in both the progression of COPD and the development of insulin resistance. The pulmonary consequences of diabetes and metabolic syndrome lead to a somewhat restrictive pattern, with significantly lower FEV1 and FVC values than in non-diabetics, and abdominal obesity seems to have a dominant role. The complexity in the management of this comorbidity includes some recognized contra-indications, for example high-dose inhaled corticosteroids are a risk factor for the development or poor control of diabetes⁸.

COPD and Heart Failure: Heart failure and COPD are diseases with very similar risk factors, particularly through the role of smoking, that share pathophysiological mechanisms, such as inflammation and skeletal muscle alterations.

Chronic heart failure (CHF) and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) occur simultaneously in a significant percentage of older patients⁹ and are characterized as modern epidemics interfering with the daily life of millions of patients¹⁰. The causes of this frequent coexistence are the common risk factors, i.e. old age, smoking, systemic inflammation. The prevalence of heart failure in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is estimated to a fifth (1: 5)¹¹. The probability for HF development is about 4 times greater in COPD patients regardless of age, and other cardiovascular risk factors¹². This relationship of diseases is confirmed by the prevalence of COPD in patients with heart failure (1/6 up to 1/3) with higher frequency in men (probably due to the smoking habit) (Hawkins NM, et al., 2009). Also the frequency of comorbidity is reduced in young ages and in very elderly¹³.

⁵ Mannino DM, Thorn D, Swensen A, et al. Prevalence and outcomes of diabetes, hypertension and cardiovascular disease in COPD. *Eur Respir J* 2008; 32: 962–969.

⁶ Watz H, Waschki B, Kirsten A, et al. The metabolic syndrome in patients with chronic bronchitis and COPD. *Chest* 2009; 136, 4: 1039 1046.

⁷ Chatila WM, Thomashow BM, Minai OA, Criner GJ, Make BJ. Comorbidities in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Proc Am Thorac Soc.* 2008;5(4):549–555.

In both diseases there are common symptoms, with dominant symptom the breathlessness during effort (Le Jemtel TH, et al., 2007). Both conditions often exhibit significant decrease in exercise tolerance. Also weakness and depressive dysthymia are usual. But there are also combinations of signs to help diagnosis. If for example in a patient diagnosed with COPD exhibits orthopnea, nocturnal paroxysmal cough accompanied with paroxysmal nocturnal dyspnea, or acute pulmonary edema, fatigue, and decreased exercise tolerance, then probably heart failure is the cause of symptoms, if there is no infection of the respiratory system⁷.

2.1.2 Identifying user requirements for the target patient segments

In order to identify the specific requirements to meet the needs of the target patient population, a series of qualitative studies were conducted. For a successful system design, user requirements of key stakeholders (healthcare professionals (HCPs), patients and informal carers) from each of the validating countries were determined as part of D2.1 to ascertain the specification of the system designed, the current challenges in the healthcare system already delivered, the perceptions and acceptance of stakeholders of the proposed system and their requirements. An interview schedule (for HCPs) and focus group schedules (for patients and carers) were devised which explored all the above issues. The qualitative study was conducted in the UK, Netherlands, Greece and Ireland. A total of 32 patients with COPD, 27 informal carers and 23 HCPs were recruited in the four countries. The findings of the study revealed the current state of care in the four countries and an understanding of how the proposed WELCOME project can be implemented to integrate care and improve patient outcomes. It also highlighted the specific needs of all stakeholders involved in COPD patients including the patients. The recommendation derived from the study findings constituted the backbone of the WELCOME system's user requirements and were instrumental in shaping the later stages of system development and design. The COPD care pathway in 5 European countries (Germany, Greece, Ireland, Netherlands & UK) were then mapped (D2.2). HCPs from the 5 countries were interviewed using a qualitative, semi-structured 2 stages email interview. The findings of these interviews were used to ensure that the WELCOME system would support the multidisciplinary integrated care approach required for the management of COPD patients in EU countries. These were the basis for the business processes and the user requirements extensively documented in D3.1 and updated in D3.2. In summary, these include a multifaceted daily monitoring of patients enhanced by technology to decrease HCP burden and highlight important and actionable information for HCPs, patient self-reporting of conditions, patient education and support, easy communication between patient and HCP, as well as among HCPs, support for the informal carer.

2.1.3 Summary

The complex nature of COPD disease necessitates an integrated coordinated approach involving a multidisciplinary team. The information included above makes clear the rationale behind the selection of quite prevalent comorbid COPD cases, as well as the complexity of these cases that highlights the need for multifaceted monitoring and coordinated management, as proposed in WELCOME. The signs and symptoms, the contraindications, etc, of these cases and the relevant knowledge is incorporated in the WELCOME Cloud DSS (reported in D3.2, D5.1). The patient applications are mapped to the needs of COPD patients, as elaborated in D2.1 'End User Requirement: Feature Identification for WELCOME system', taking into account comorbidities. These were the basis for the business processes and system requirements elaborated in D3.1 and further enhanced in D3.2.

⁷ Chhabra SK, Gupta M. Coexistent chronic obstructive pulmonary disease-heart failure: mechanisms, diagnostic and therapeutic dilemmas. Indian J Chest Dis Allied Sci 2010;52:225-38.

As defined in D2.3 (Established Model for Implementation of the WELCOME System in Pilot Countries), WELCOME system overall considers patients with confirmed diagnosis of COPD (stage II to IV) irrespective of oxygen dependency, and at any age (40-90yrs), and having specific comorbidities: diabetes, heart failure, anxiety/depression. Although the WELCOME system has a potential to positively influence the management of all COPD patients, it's anticipated that higher risk patients who are associated with poorer outcomes are likely to benefit the most. Therefore, the target segments of patients are those who have COPD stage III or IV, particularly patients with concurrent comorbidities. Earlier stages were not in focus as the probability of symptoms and exacerbations, and thus the need for early diagnosis via telemedicine is considered low. COPD stage I patients are completely excluded from the study.

Which patient segments will benefit more, and from which parts, remains to be analysed based on the pilot data, especially as regards the early detection of different deteriorations and conditions around them, the and secondarily the patient management and education modules. This is expected to help future fine-tuning and enhancing functionality for COPD management, e.g. by improving the DSS with respect to early or late COPD stages, or specific comorbidities, or by future inclusion of tailored unsupervised lifestyle interventions⁸.

2.2 Clinical Workflows, users' cooperation, privacy and security issues

The current care pathways were initially described in D2.2 (A Streamlined Care Pathway Model Incorporating the WELCOME System as a Tool of Care). Specifically, the care pathway for patients with COPD was compared between five countries: England, Ireland, Netherlands, Greece and Germany, in order to explore the similarities and differences in diagnosis, follow-up and services provided to patients to manage COPD. The diagnostics parameters, normal ranges, therapeutic targets and alerts values for COPD patients are only slightly different between the five countries. The follow-up care services (e.g. pulmonary rehabilitation (PR)) differ largely between countries, as regards also the role of primary care. In the five countries, the same management of COPD is followed even if the patients are being diagnosed with co-morbidities. Each co-morbidity is managed independently following its own national guidelines and providing its own services (e.g. clinical teams...). The services being provided for lifestyle management are similar between the five countries. Smoking cessation, advice on annual flu vaccination, advice on importance of PR and referral to dieticians are example of such services. The patients' adherence to therapy is monitored differently.

This section presents in detail the mapping of the WELCOME business processes (defined in D3.1 and updated in D3.2) to the existing workflows adopted by the clinical governance systems of the countries that are participating in the project's pilot studies (presented in D2.2). The business processes, and thus the clinical workflows, are then correlated to the available WELCOME system functionality. To elaborate more on the HCP collaboration for integrated care in COPD comorbidity, basic scenario are further discussed.

2.2.1 WELCOME User system roles update

In D3.2, the WELCOME User system roles are presented, accompanied with a description of what actions users with these roles can perform in the WELCOME system. The initial approach presented in D3.2 was that a user may have multiple roles in the context of the WELCOME system. After serious

⁸ P. A. Coventry, P. Bower, C. Keyworth, C. Kenning, J. Knopp, C. Garrett, D. Hind, A. Malpass, and C. Dickens, "The Effect of Complex Interventions on Depression and Anxiety in Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis," PLoS One, vol. 8, no. 4, 2013.

consideration, and given the fact that the assignment of multiple roles to a WELCOME user may lead to inconsistencies and wrong assumptions as regards the access rights and the allowed actions per application, we reached a consensus for the definitions of the WELCOME user system roles.

The available WELCOME User system roles remain as they are defined in D3.2 and Figure 38 of the same document still applies. The change we introduce in the present document is that there is no more multiplicity in the assignments of roles. The assumption we made earlier when we stated that multiple roles are assigned to a user, especially in the cases Clinical Admin/P-HCP and Clinical Admin/NPHCP, are no longer valid. This change primarily affects the actions that users with the Clinical Administrator and HCP roles, both P-HCP and NP-HCP, can perform in the system. In the following, we redefine these roles, while the Patient and Informal Carer roles remain the same. The “Gatekeeper” and secondary attribute roles per patient also remain unaffected.

Section 2.2.5 describes in detail the access rights and allowed actions the WELCOME user system roles can perform per User application. The updated D6.1 and D6.2 of WP6 present updated use cases for the changes mentioned previously in the role hierarchy and in compliance with Section 2.2.5.

Clinical Administrator:

The users with the Clinical Administrator role are responsible for the system users’ management (HCPs, patients and informal carers), as well as the management of the equipment related to the WELCOME system. Clinical Administrators and HCPs perform the patient registration by themselves; in a hospital environment, rarely are HCPs involved in the administrative tasks of the patient registration. Members of the nursing staff may be involved in some cases; however this is the exception and not the rule. Usually, a designated group exists that registers and manages patients.

In general, the registration of patients, HCPs and informal carers in an integrated care system, such as the WELCOME project, needs central management. A patient does not always seek treatment in a hospitalized environment. GPs and other private doctors or other specialties may as well be the first points of treatment for patients. It is therefore imperative for an integrated system that spans from hospitalized environment to private doctors to allow HCPs to register patients directly.

For this reason, we decide to allow P-HCP users to be able to partially manage directly their patients, allowing to register them in the WELCOME system, without the need to contact a Clinical Administrator. From a privacy point of view, on one hand we define the HCPs access rights in such a way, so that they can access the Clinical Administration applications themselves. On the other hand, they are only able to view and manage their own patients (and whatever devices or carers accompany them) or register new ones. Section 2.2.5 presents in a clear manner the access conditions of users with the P-HCP role.

P-PHCP & NP-PHCP (Prescriber and Non-Prescriber Health Care Professionals):

In D3.2, we presented several decisions with regards to the roles of the Prescriber and Non-Prescriber HCPs. In the following, we present changes that we make to these initial decisions:

- A patient seeking treatment will need to be registered initially either by a Clinical Administrator or by a Prescriber HCP. When the patient is successfully registered in the system, an HCP needs to be assigned to that patient for future treatments. The assignment of this HCP to this patient will be performed by one of the following two ways:
 - Either the Clinical Administrator will assign the patient to a Prescriber HCP, who will become the Gatekeeper HCP (therefore Primary) for that patient

- Or the Prescriber HCP who originally registered the patient in the system will become his/her Gatekeeper HCP

The association of a HCP with a patient remains critical, as it provides access rights to the patient's medical records. Instead of keeping the previous complexity of a central authority confirming the assignment, we delegate this responsibility to the original WELCOME user (Clinical Admin or HCP) who registered the patient in the system.

- The fact remains that the first HCP that the patient turns to in order to seek treatment is considered as the "gate-keeping" HCP. This HCP will be responsible for the treatment and monitoring of COPD. In the case of comorbidities being present and the patient needs referral to other specialist HCPs, then the "gate-keeper" HCP will send invitations (via the relevant application) to other HCPs of different specialties registered in the system. At this point, we remove the complexity of letting the Clinical Admin confirm the assignments. Should the other HCPs accept them, they are automatically assigned and are considered members of the patient monitoring team. In case of invitation rejection, the Gatekeeper HCP retains the right to further invite HCPs, until the final formation of the team.
- All co-operating HCPs, either the "gate-keeper" or the invited HCPs for comorbidities, share essentially the same access rights on the overall treatment of a patient. As every HCP is a specialist in his/her own field, no special rights over the patient treatment need to be considered. Essentially, all HCPs treating and monitoring a patient will have access to the full functionality provided by the HCP application. The Prescriber HCPs will be able to contribute their own data regarding the medical history of the patient, view vital signs and measurements (not necessarily restricted to their own specialty) and prescribe medication to the patient. The Non-Prescriber HCPs however cannot prescribe medication, due to their role nature. Section 2.2.4 and deliverables of WP6 (D6.1, D6.2) present specific details on the collaboration scheme between different HCPs monitoring a single patient.

2.2.2 Summary of business processes and care pathways

WELCOME proposes, for the diverse schemes of COPD care in different countries, the addition of the telemedicine and integrated care management program. The WELCOME system recognizes the complexity of integrated care for COPD and comorbidities, and therefore, adopts a set of the roles for management, as described in D3.2 (clinical admin, Prescriber and Non-Prescriber HCP with the gatekeeper property). For example, the GP in UK and by the expert pulmonologist in Greece undertake typically the gatekeeper property, without a conflict as regards the WELCOME system.

Indeed, the gatekeeper is the HCP to whom the patient mostly refers, who is in closest contact and communication and has an overview of the case, and can support the HCP collaboration. As stated in D3.2, the gatekeeper is not a different role, but rather a property of an HCP. The Clinical Admin assigns this property to an HCP when registering a new patient.

The clinical administrator role is related to the telemedicine service suggested by WELCOME, and the administrative tasks around it.

We do not consider being the gatekeeper and the clinical administrator as one, as the former is a role, and the latter is on a per-patient property. Of note, whether one actual person taken more than one roles, it is a matter of choice, with the exception of a prescribing and non-prescribing HCP, which are mutually exclusive.

As regards the clinical administration, in future systems, this could be expanded to a hierarchy around the administrator, to include a program manager and program staff.

Table 1 presents in summary the WELCOME project functionalities and system user roles that satisfy the defined business processes of D3.1 and D3.2. Section 2.2.5 provides further details on the user rights and access policy for the HCP applications.

Each business process in Table 1 is linked with a related clinical workflow description, the allowed system user roles and a reference to the WELCOME functionality that serves this requirement.

Table 1. Updated business processes' list

BP	Label	Relation to clinical workflow description	System roles involved (Clinical Admin, Prescribing HCP, Non Prescribing HCP, Patient, Carer, Gatekeeper ⁹)	Graphical interface of BP implementation
BP-01	HCP registers patient	<p>BP01a: Patient registration procedure</p> <p>BP01b: Device-tools registration/assignment based on communication within the HCP team. This is optionally asynchronous and repeatable. Not all devices are assigned to the patient upon registration. The arisen need to monitor a comorbidity may pose the need to assign a related device at a later point in time.</p>	<p>BP01a: Clinical Admin, P-HCP</p> <p>BP01b: Clinical Admin, P-HCP, Gatekeeper</p>	<p>BP01a: Clinical Administrator application (Figure 25 , Figure 26).</p> <p>BP01b: Assignment and registration of devices is presented in Figure 27, Figure 28. Drag and drop assignment of devices is presented in Figure 29.</p> <p>The message exchange module of the HCP application is extended to include inter-HCP messages. This extension is intended for asynchronous and repeatable communication between HCPs. In this case, communication related to extra device assignments after initial registration in the HCP team will use this module.</p>

⁹ Gatekeeper is considered a P-HCP user role attribute on a per-patient basis, rather than a system role. It is accompanying the system roles in the above table, as a finer level of detail for understanding the central role of a “Gatekeeper” HCP inside a multi-disciplinary team of HCPs.

BP-02	HCP trains patient to use the vest and additional devices	The Gatekeeper (P-HCP) or NP-HCP can train the patient and the carer.	Patient, Carer, Gatekeeper, P-HCP, NP-HCP	<p>A face-to-face meeting takes place where the Gatekeeper (P-HCP) or NP-HCP trains the patients and informal carers on the use of the WELCOME vest and additional devices. This is an offline event and is not recorded in the WELCOME system.</p> <p>Additional training material in the form of device manuals can be set up by the HCP in the respective Training Modules of the HCP and Patient/Carer applications for future reference.</p>
BP-03	HCP/System admin gives the patient the device package pre-configured	<p>The Gatekeeper (P-HCP) or NP-HCP will provide the patient with the system package. The process is performed in two steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The Gatekeeper HCP or Clinical Admin pre-assigns the devices to that specific patient in the Clinical Administration application. 2) A face-to-face meeting takes place where the device package is delivered to the patient by the HCP. <p>The devices are preconfigured and are ready to be used by the</p>	Patient, Gatekeeper, P-HCP, NP-HCP, Clinical Admin	<p>The device assignment to a patient is performed via the Clinical Administration application. This is similar to the BP-01b process, described earlier. The device assignment procedure is depicted in Figure 27, Figure 28 and Figure 29.</p> <p>The face-to-face meeting where the devices are given to the patient preconfigured takes place offline.</p>

		patient.		
BP-04	HCP defines the patient's schedule for treatment/management/recording	The Gatekeeper defines the parameters regarding the scheduled use of the system including rehabilitation and smoking cessation programs. (this BP is updated)	Gatekeeper, P-HCP	<p>The HCPs are able to configure explicitly the patient's schedule regarding the system means of treatment, management and recording. The HCP application offers the ability to configure independently per patient the vest and external medical devices recording times, the questionnaire schedule, the rehabilitation and the smoking cessation programs. The HCP application could additionally offer predefined bundles of questionnaires, questionnaire times and device measurement times which could be assigned to patients upon registration to the system. Per measurement or per questionnaire timing direction configuration for the patients could prove to be a time consuming task for a HCP.</p> <p>A derived functionality is the assignment of questionnaires (on demand or scheduled) to patients by the HCPs. This functionality is realized in the HCP application Questionnaire module, where the HCP can select existing questionnaires (or insert new, not available in the system ones) and subsequently assign them to the desired patient(s). The questionnaire assignment is accompanied by scheduling information, providing timing guidance on their completion by the</p>

				<p>patient and carer.</p> <p>The patient or carer can use the Calendar module of the respective applications in order to retrieve critical timing information (Figure 32). Notifications are also produced as reminders prior to the times set by the HCP.</p>
BP-05	HCP examines Patient at outpatient clinic or GP office	The examination procedure may be held at the outpatients department of a hospital or at private practice setting	Patient, possibly Gatekeeper, (P and NP) HCP	This is a process that takes place offline and is not reflected in the WELCOME system. However, the results of this offline HCP – Patient meeting can effectively be handled by BP-06.
BP-06	HCP registers Patient hospitalization related information	After hospitalization the system must be updated with all relevant data	Gatekeeper,P-HCP, NP-HCP	<p>Medical findings related to the patient’s condition may arise during a private examination by a HCP or during patient hospitalization. The HCP can register hospitalization related information or any other form of medical findings during a private examination in the HCP application for future reference (Figure 33).</p> <p>Information entered in the module can be accessed by all cooperating HCPs in the case of a multi-disciplinary team of HCPs monitoring a patient.</p>
BP-07	Patient wears vest and records data	When at home the patient uses the vest and the data are automatically transmitted to the WELCOME cloud	Patient	The patient uses the vest which has been given to him/her in BP-01b according to the instructions provided in BP-02. The Data Collection application receives measurement data and uploads them to the WELCOME Cloud for

				storage and further processing (Figure 34).
BP-08	Patient measures data with external devices	When at home the patient uses the external devices and the data are automatically transmitted to the WELCOME clouds	Patient	The patient uses the external devices that have been given to him/her in BP-01b according to the instructions provided in BP-02. The measurement process is initiated through the Data Collection application. Recorded measurement data are uploaded to the WELCOME Cloud for storage and further processing (Figure 35).
BP-09	Patients (potentially with the help of the informal carer) answers questionnaires	When at home the patient uses the tablet to fill in the assigned to him/her questionnaires	Patient, Carer	The patient and carer use the Questionnaire module of the respective applications to answer and review the questionnaires that have been assigned by a HCP that monitors the patient (Figure 36).
BP-10	Patient/carers can access schedule	When at home patient is informed about his treatment and measurement schedule	Patient, Carer	The Patient/ Carer application Diary module (Figure 37) provides information on the device measurement and questionnaire times, as well as the appointments with a HCP.
BP-11	Patient/carers can access own recorded data	When at home the patient may access his own recorded data	Patient, Carer	The patient and carer can access their own recorded data through the Patient/Carer application History Module (Figure 38, Figure 39). The patient in particular can access their measurement history only in the case that the Gatekeeper HCP has allowed it (due to the psychological effect this may have on the patient).

BP-12	Patient/carer exchange private messages	Patient or carer may exchange private messages with HCPs	P-HCP, NP-HCP, patient, carer	The HCP and patient/Carer applications share a messaging module which can be used for the exchange of private messages between HCPs and patient/carers. Figure 40 displays the HCP application messaging module, where the HCP has exchanged some messages with the patient.
BP-13	Patient may receive schedule reminders and HCP originated notifications	Patient and carer receive personalized messages and notifications created by HCPs	Patient, carer, P-HCP, NP-HCP	The Patient/Carer applications generate notifications and reminders when the vest and external devices measurements need to be taken and the questionnaires need to be answered and submitted.
BP-14	Patient may access educational content	The patient when at home may access educational content selected by his/her HCPs	Patient, NP-HCP, P-HCP	<p>Patients and carers need educational content on their medical condition and the usage of the system's devices (vest and external devices). This educational material is set up by the HCPs that monitor a patient and can be managed via the Educational module of the HCP application.</p> <p>The patient/carer can access the educational material set up by a HCP in the respective Educational module of the Patient/Carer applications.</p>
BP-15	HCP can access recent and longitudinal patient data in a timely fashion	HCPs may access longitudinal patient data	Gatekeeper, NP-HCP, P-HCP	Review of both the History (Figure 33), the DSS alerts (Figure 43) and the Measurements module (Figure 41, Figure 42) in the HCP application provides access to recent and longitudinal patient

				data in a timely fashion.
BP-16	HCP must register and communicate current changes in treatment plan	P-HCPs may change treatment of the patient and this change must be communicated (via traditional methods) and subsequently recorded to the system.	P-HCP, patient	<p>Prescriber HCPs may identify the need to change the patient treatment plan at a given point in time. This change needs to be communicated to the patient first via the traditional established methods (in a face to face meeting with the patient). This change in the treatment plan may either relate to a change in the medication plan, or a change in the WELCOME device measurement times.</p> <p>At a later point, the decided change in the medication plan needs to be reflected in the system, so that the patient can conform to it.</p> <p>Every HCP may suggest a change in the patient medication plan, even if the medication has been prescribed by a different fellow HCP, and communicate this suggestion to the HCP team along with sufficient justification, in the form of a message/notification. The original HCP prescriber performs the necessary medication plan change, which will be propagated to the HCP team. This feature facilitates a faster treatment adoption to the medical condition, overcoming the traditional time consuming communication means between HCPs, without</p>

				compromising the need for coordination among experts.
BP-17	HCP can log patient progress and comments	HCP may log to the system conditions and disease progress after patient visit.	P-HCP, NP-HCP	Information on the patient's medical condition can be logged in the WELCOME system via the HCP application History module (Figure 33). All the HCPs that are monitoring the specific patient (on COPD and comorbidities) are able to log patient progress, medical data and personal comments on the patient condition. The full medical history of the patient is available to all of the HCPs that monitor the patient; management however of discrete records in the patient history is allowed only to the original author/contributor.
BP-18	HCP can answer patient questions	Patient or carer may exchange private messages regarding patient questions with HCPs. Questions may be about usage of devices or medical subjects.	NP-HCP, P-HCP, patient, carer	This is similar to BP-12 .
BP-19	HCP can request an out-of-schedule follow-up	Based on monitored information a Prescriber HCP may request a visit in person	P-HCP, patient	<p>The HCP may deem important to schedule a new appointment with a patient when there is an abnormality in the recorded information (measurements and questionnaires). The appointment can be set up by the Diary module of the HCP application.</p> <p>The patient, upon schedule of such an appointment, will receive a notification in the</p>

				<p>Patient application. The appointment will be visible in the Patient application Diary module (Figure 32).</p>
BP-20	<p>System supports HCP coordination among specialists for comorbidities treatment.</p>	<p>Includes formation of HCP team via invitations initiated by Gatekeeper with restriction of one by specialty.</p>	P-HCP, NP-HCP	<p>The WELCOME system provides a mechanism for the formation of multi-disciplinary teams of HCPs with the intention of monitoring a patient with COPD and comorbidities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Invitation mechanism initiated by the Gatekeeper HCP. The Gatekeeper can use the in-system invitation mechanism to ask fellow HCPs of different specialties to monitor a specific patient. In the case of rejection, the Gatekeeper can send new invitations. However, a restriction of only one HCP of a specific specialty being a member of a multi-disciplinary team for the same patient applies. - HCPs can change the treatment plan of a patient per BP-16. In-system, inter-HCP notifications are generated whenever a change occurs in a patient's treatment plan, so that all HCPs are aware. In particular, changes in the medication plan and the device recording times will generate notifications, so that this information is shared among HCPs. - HCPs can contribute to the medical history records of the patient via the HCP application History module. All HCPs

				are allowed to create entries and all entries are visible to all the members of the team. However, management of an entry is only allowed to the original author.
BP-21	HCP checks the patient's compliance to medicine and lifestyle treatment	Using the WELCOME system the HCP may review the patients compliance to inhaler medication administration	P-HCP, NP-HCP	HCPs are able to review the compliance of their patients to medication and lifestyle treatment based on the device measurements and the questionnaire responses from patients.
BP-22	HCP gets hints/notifications	The system based on the WELCOME DSS provides almost real-time hints/notifications regarding patient condition based on the tele monitored data	P-HCP, NP-HCP	<p>The HCP may review the DSS alerts that have been generated by the WELCOME Cloud in the DSS Notifications/Alerts module of the HCP application (Figure 43).</p> <p>Whenever an alert is generated for a patient monitored by the HCP user of the application, an on-screen message will be displayed.</p>

2.2.3 The Clinical Pathways

The national care pathway diagrams of deliverable D2.2 (Appendix D) are used as basis in an effort to properly reflect the association between the existing care pathway interactions in the Greek, German, Dutch, British and Irish Care system with the WELCOME project business processes and the defined system user roles.

Figure 2-Figure 6 present in detail the mapping of the existing national care pathways to the WELCOME business processes, as elaborated by WP2 partners. It includes the different stakeholders and how they interact. Apart from the existing entities in the pathways, the diagrams include the WELCOME Cloud and the Patient Hub, which are not part of the existing clinical pathways, but are rather introduced by the WELCOME project. All the participating entities are marked with the allowed WELCOME system user roles. The diagrams mark the possible interactions (new or extensions) between the care pathway participants. These interactions are clearly marked with the WELCOME system business processes that they serve.

With respect to the medication management, these figures clearly present who are the prescriber HCPs (P-HCP), also involved in BP-16, and who are the NP-HCPS in each national system.

The BPs are summarised below.

BP-01	HCP registers patient
BP-02	HCP trains patient to use the vest and additional devices
BP-03	HCP/System admin gives the patient the device package pre-configured
BP-04	HCP defines the patient's schedule for treatment/management/recording
BP-05	HCP examines Patient at outpatient clinic or GP office
BP-06	HCP registers Patient hospitalization related information
BP-07	Patient wears vest and records data
BP-08	Patient measures data with external devices
BP-09	Patients (potentially with the help of the informal carer) answers questionnaires
BP-10	Patient/carers can access schedule
BP-11	Patient/carers can access own recorded data
BP-12	Patient/carers exchange private messages
BP-13	Patient may receive schedule reminders and HCP originated notifications
BP-14	Patient may access educational content
BP-15	HCP can access recent and longitudinal patient data in a timely fashion
BP-16	HCP must register and communicate current changes in treatment plan
BP-17	HCP can log patient progress and comments
BP-18	HCP can answer patient questions
BP-19	HCP can request an out-of-schedule follow-up
BP-20	System supports HCP coordination among specialists for comorbidities treatment.
BP-21	HCP checks the patient's compliance to medicine and lifestyle treatment
BP-22	HCP gets hints/notifications

Listing 1: WELCOME business processes in summary

The Greek care pathway

Figure 2: Greek care pathway with mapped WELCOME business processes

The German care pathway

Figure 3: German care pathway with mapped WELCOME business processes

The UK care pathway

Figure 4: UK care pathway with mapped WELCOME business processes

The Ireland care pathway

Figure 5: Irish care pathway with mapped WELCOME business processes

The Netherlands care pathway

Figure 6: Dutch care pathway with mapped WELCOME business processes

2.2.4 HCP collaboration in comorbidity management

WELCOME incorporates the ability to support several variations of care workflows and a set of rules has been developed to facilitate adaptable workflow in terms of HCPs' cooperation for any given patient in the WELCOME platform. The workflow will be in agreement with the differences in healthcare management occurring in each European country.

The following listing highlights the BPs that are mainly involved in collaboration among HCPs for comorbidity management.

BP-15	HCP can access recent and longitudinal patient data in a timely fashion
BP-16	HCP must register and communicate current changes in treatment plan
BP-17	HCP can log patient progress and comments
BP-18	HCP can answer patient questions
BP-19	HCP can request an out-of-schedule follow-up
BP-20	System supports HCP coordination among specialists for comorbidities treatment.
BP-21	HCP checks the patient's compliance to medicine and lifestyle treatment
BP-22	HCP gets hints/notifications

Listing 2. WELCOME business processes addressing comorbidity management among HCPs.

In order to better explore WELCOME based comorbidity, the definition of a care workflow for collaborative medication management is attempted, based on the input by WELCOME consortium experts. A general outline of the model is depicted in Figure 7. This is mapped to BP-16 as regards medication change, and BP-20 as regards HCP collaboration. In this case, the Cardiologist is defined as prescribing HCP, member of the comorbidity management team, after invitation of the gatekeeper.

Figure 7: Medication Scenario 1 - A simple medication update example

A more complicated example is depicted in Figure 8. Here the request for treatment change is not raised by the P-HCP who originally prescribed the medication. In this case the collaboration and agreement of the involved experts is needed to complete the change. Of note, WELCOME does not handle emergency cases where medication might be temporarily changed, for example during hospitalisations. Any relevant hospitalization information, if available, is registered in the system by the gatekeeper (BP-06).

Figure 8: Medication Scenario 2: A more complicated medication update example, which entails

The above schema represents a generic workflow for care co-operation in terms of governance rules and can be updated with changes according to specific limitations and/or different common practices in each country. For example, it can host different specialties in the management of COPD and comorbid conditions and add further physician entries (in case of the diagnosis of a new comorbidity) and also change the role of the gatekeeper in every national healthcare setting (the GP in the UK or the pulmonologist in Greece).

It is clear that the main role of the gatekeeper ensures the smooth workflow among the HCPs involved and is responsible for the conflicts resolution in certain cases. The design of the smart rules embedded in the WELCOME Medical Decision Support System foresees that the messages or alerts generated by the system will be addressed to the related physicians for further evaluation, generating subsequent workflows that are orchestrated by the gatekeeper and stick to the pattern of similar workflows exercised in every country. The following example depicts the collaboration actions between two HCPs in the case of an alert generated by the system:

Figure 9: HCP collaboration related to an alert.

The WELCOME set of rules affecting the realization of the aforementioned workflows can be preset before the employment of the system in every different healthcare setting, ensuring its compliance with the special provisions in every country. In this context, the person acting as the gatekeeper will be assigned according to the common practice in the specific region and the definition of an HCP's role as a prescribing or non-prescribing physician will be based on the local legislation and rules.

The examples depicted above constitute an initial attempt to leverage the collaboration dynamics among HPCs, by setting clear roles, and by facilitating communication and information sharing via WELCOME system. Clearly, based on future experience by using the system, these scenarios can be further fine-tuned.

2.2.5 Main points on privacy and security policy

User Applications' Access Rights per WELCOME user role

The section below describes the allowed actions that the WELCOME system user roles are authorised to perform per application. For every different User application, a table listing allowed actions per role exists. There are also additional numbered notes that further explain certain assumptions that accompany some of the allowed actions, below each table.

Clinical Administration Application

Table 2: Clinical Administration access rights

Allowed Application Actions for Role	ADMIN	P-HCP	NP-HCP	PATIENT	CARER
View patients	X ¹	X ³	-	-	-
View carers	X ¹	X ⁴	-	-	-
View all HCPs	X ¹	X	-	-	-
View devices	X ¹	X ⁵	-	-	-

Registration of patients	X	X	-	-	-
Registration of HCPs	X	-	-	-	-
Registration of carers	X	X	-	-	-
Registration of devices	X	X	-	-	-
Device assignment/dissociation to patient	X	X ⁶	-	-	-
Carer assignment/ dissociation to patient	X	X ⁷	-	-	-
HCP assignment to patient	X ²	X ⁸	-	-	-
HCP dissociation from patient	X	X ⁹	-	-	-

Users with NP-HCP, Patient and Carer roles are not allowed access to the Clinical Administration application, therefore there are no access rights for these roles. The following notes are explanatory of the items marked in Table 2.

1.	Refers to only private, user related data. By no means is the access to WELCOME Cloud stored medical data possible through the Clinical Administration application.
2.	ADMIN users are allowed to assign HCPs to a patient only if there is no other HCP assigned: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The first assigned HCP should always be the PRIMARY for that patient An invitation is sent to that HCP with PRIMARY notation On invitation acceptance, the assignment is complete The user with ADMIN cannot send any further invitations, only the PRIMARY HCP is responsible for further strengthening the HCP team.
3.	P-HCP users can <ul style="list-style-type: none"> View patients not currently assigned to any HCP users (P-HCP or NP-HCP) View own patients (either when related as PRIMARY or as SECONDARY)
4.	P-HCP users can <ul style="list-style-type: none"> View carers not currently assigned to any HCP users (P-HCP or NP-HCP) View carers of own patients (either when related to these patients as PRIMARY or as SECONDARY)
5.	P-HCP users can <ul style="list-style-type: none"> View devices not currently assigned to any patient users View devices currently assigned to own patients (either when related to these patients as PRIMARY or as SECONDARY)
6.	P-HCP users can assign or dissociate devices to own patients, only if HCP is PRIMARY for that patient

7.	P-HCP users can assign or dissociate carers to own patients, only if HCP is PRIMARY for that patient
8.	<p>P-HCP users can:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assign themselves to orphan patients <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ In case of self-assignment, they are assigned as PRIMARY HCPs ○ Assignment is direct (no invitation involved) • Assignment of other HCPs to patients <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for patients for which the P-HCP user is a PRIMARY HCP ○ Invitations are issued towards the other HCP
9.	<p>P-HCP users can:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • remove themselves from an assigned patient (previously being either PRIMARY or SECONDARY) • remove all SECONDARY HCPs from a patient for whom the current P-HCP user is PRIMARY

Health Care Professional Application

Table 3: Health Care Professional access rights

Allowed Application Actions for Role	ADMIN	P-HCP	NP-HCP	PATIENT	CARER
View all assigned patients on the dashboard	-	X	X	-	-
View and select close monitoring patients on the dashboard	-	X	X	-	-
View patients with alerts on the dashboard	-	X	X	-	-
View all medical history record excerpts, regardless of the original author HCP	-	X	X	-	-
Create new excerpt in the existing medical history record	-	X	-	-	-
Edit his/her own medical record excerpts	-	X	-	-	-
View all patient vital signs	-	X	X	-	-
View all patient notifications and alerts	-	X	X	-	-
View all existing in-system static questionnaires	-	X	X	-	-
Create new questionnaires	-	X	X	-	-
View all questionnaires created by him/her	-	X	X	-	-
View all questionnaires responses of his/her patients	-	X ¹	X ¹	-	-

Assign questionnaires to patients (both existing static ones and the ones created by him/her)	-	X	X	-	-
View all existing prescribed medication	-	X	X	-	-
Add medication prescription	-	X	-	-	-
Edit his/her own originally prescribed medication	-	X	-	-	-
Send message to other prescriber HCPs belonging to the same team monitoring the patient when an update to an existing medication is required.	-	X	-	-	-
Exchange of messages with their patients	-	X	X	-	-
View instructions on devices usage	-	X	X	-	-
Post instructions on devices usage to their patients	-	X ²	-	-	-
Assign patient modules and programs	-	X ³	-	-	-
View educational material set up for that patient	-	X	X	-	-
Manage educational material for that patient	-	X ⁴	X ⁴	-	-

Users with Admin, Patient and Carer roles are not allowed access to the Health Care Professional application, therefore there no access rights for these roles. The following notes are explanatory of the items marked in Table 3.

1.	P-HCP/NP-HCP can see all questionnaires responses of the patients assigned to them, but only the responses for questionnaires that have been originally assigned by them
2.	Only if the P-HCP user is assigned as the PRIMARY HCP for that patient
3.	Only if the P-HCP user is assigned as the PRIMARY HCP for that patient
4.	<p>Management of educational material by a P-HCP user allowed is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set up new educational material for an assigned patient (either being assigned as PRIMARY or SECONDARY) Edit or remove educational material, only if he/she is the original material contributor for that part

Patient Application

Table 4: Patient Application access rights

Allowed Application Actions for Role	ADMIN	P-HCP	NP-HCP	PATIENT	CARER
View all assigned questionnaires	-	-	-	X	-

Filling and submitting questionnaires	-	-	-	X	-
Access the Data Collection application	-	-	-	X	-
View list of prescribed medications	-	-	-	X	-
View diary displaying appointments, medications, questionnaires and measurements to be taken	-	-	-	X	-
Receive reminders about measurements, questionnaires, medications and appointments	-	-	-	X	-
View educational materials based on different assigned programs	-	-	-	X	-
View history	-	-	-	X	-
Send comments to assigned healthcare professionals	-	-	-	X	-
Search for weather in current location or worldwide	-	-	-	X	-

Users with Admin, P-HCP, NP-HCP and Carer roles are not allowed access to the Patient application, therefore there no access rights for these roles.

Patient Data Collection Application

Table 5: Patient Data Collection application access rights

Allowed Application Actions for Role	ADMIN	P-HCP	NP-HCP	PATIENT	CARER
View a list of assigned devices	-	-	-	X	-
Select measurement type/icon from the Measurement user interface of the application (External devices/Vest Streaming/Vest Download)	-	-	-	X	-
Use external medical devices to take measurements	-	-	-	X	-
Wear the vest to collect readings	-	-	-	X	-
View progress bar of data streaming from the vest and sound recording	-	-	-	X	-
View battery life	-	-	-	X	-
Start/Stop the microphone recording on the vest	-	-	-	X	-
Access patient application to view diary/complete questionnaires as described in the table above.	-	-	-	X	-

Users with Admin, P-HCP, NP-HCP and Carer roles are not allowed access to the Patient Data Collection application, therefore there no access rights for these roles.

Informal Carer Application

Table 6: Informal Carer Application access rights

Allowed Application Actions for Role	ADMIN	P-HCP	NP-HCP	PATIENT	CARER
View all assigned questionnaires	-	-	-	-	X
Filling and submitting questionnaires	-	-	-	-	X
View list of prescribed medications for patient	-	-	-	-	X
View own diary and patient's diary displaying appointments, medications, questionnaires and measurements to be taken	-	-	-	-	X
Receive reminders about patient's measurements, questionnaires, medications and appointments	-	-	-	-	X
View educational materials based on different assigned programs	-	-	-	-	X
View history of patient (if patient agrees upon registration)	-	-	-	-	X
Send comments to assigned healthcare professionals	-	-	-	-	X
Search for weather in current location or worldwide	-	-	-	-	X

Users with Admin, P-HCP, NP-HCP and Patient roles are not allowed access to the Informal Carer application, therefore there no access rights for these roles.

Different sites support

Figure 42 ("Security infrastructure organization in WELCOME") of D3.2 shows multiple installations of the Organisation Hub at multiple locations, while the positioning of the WELCOME Users in the diagram may be confusing as to where these users exist. Figure 10 attempts to clear this confusion by correctly placing the users and the Organisation Hub instances inside a WELCOME system installation.

Figure 10: Users across WELCOME installations

The Organisation Hub is installed at multiple sites, specifically in each medical organisation. Each Organisation Hub stores safely its own users’ private data and links to their anonymized information in the WELCOME Cloud. The different Organisation Hub installations are completely isolated. Privacy wise, users’ private data are kept isolated at different sites. Cross-site access to private data is not possible. Access to the Organisation Hub and it’s co-deployed User applications is allowed only to its own registered users, as each Organisation Hub have independent Authentication/Authorisation servers. Security wise, each medical organisation carries the burden of properly deploying and securing its own instance of the Organisation Hub. In addition, the WELCOME Cloud and Organisation Hub security integration contains a mechanism that enables the security integration to be Organisation Hub location aware. It is not possible for a user in one Organisation Hub to be able to access private data in another location.

We consider a larger scale deployment of the Organisation Hub in a regional or national manner, where different users at different sites can access data at different locations, as future work and do not currently investigate this possibility.

Private Data Pseudonymisation

Section 4.4.4.3 of the updated D3.2 presents in detail the pseudonymisation of private data in the WELCOME Cloud. In the following, we present additional information, in sequence diagram form, in an effort to make clearer the proper use of the cloud reference identifiers and how these identifiers are used when accessing data on the WELCOME Cloud.

Figure 11: Sample Patient registration process, OH and Cloud

The newly registered patient user in the system because of Figure 11 is now available in both the Organisation Hub and the Welcome Cloud (as a reference). Only this specific Organisation Hub instance is aware of this patient. Without it, the patient resources stored in the WELCOME Cloud are impossible to be traced back to that specific patient.

Figure 12: WELCOME Cloud resource request

Figure 12 demonstrates the use of the cloud reference when requesting resources from the WELCOME Cloud. In conjunction with the fact that, as described previously, the cloud reference can only be retrieved from one instance of the OH, depending on where the owner resides, it is made clear that traceability of the WELCOME stored data back to their owners is impossible without the cloud reference.

Security Integration between Organisation Hub and the WELCOME Cloud

The details of the security integration between the Organisation Hub instances and the Welcome Cloud services is presented in detail in D3.2 (Section 4.4.4.8), along with an example diagram of a

request for Cloud resources being authenticated. For clarity purposes, we provide an additional diagram that demonstrates the communication flow between the User applications, the WELCOME Cloud services and an instance of the Organisation Hub.

Figure 13: WELCOME inter-system communication

2.3 The WELCOME Cloud Services rationale

The WELCOME cloud services architecture is comprised of multiple independent modules in order to facilitating their independent development and testing. An overview of the cloud service architecture is depicted in Figure 14 and details for the respective modules have been provided in D3.1 and D3.2.

Figure 14: WELCOME cloud system overview

The architecture's rationale is that WELCOME Cloud Communications API acts as the main front-end of the overall cloud platform, accepting requests from client applications, namely the patient hub and the HCP web applications. Typically, these requests refer to CRUD operations directly executed through the WELCOME Storage Engine (SE). Orchestrator Agent (OA) handles the complex information handling workflows, either triggered by specific events/calls on the communications API or autonomously triggered periodically. OA would typically communication with Feature Extraction Server (FES) in order to analyze the incoming raw signals data and then store the results through the SE. Furthermore, OA would trigger the respective DSS module providing complex rule evaluation functionality. Finally, OA would also trigger the execution of the External Sources Connector (ESC) which retrieves environmental data from independent web services.

2.4 The Cloud-based Decision Support System

In this subsection we elaborate on WELCOME cloud DSS details, and especially try to shed more light on how the DSS makes use of the real-time sensing and feature extraction from the one side, and the medical empirical or evidence based knowledge from the other side, towards providing clinically relevant information for diagnosis and treatment.

Figure 15: Overview of WELCOME data relevant for HCP decision making

The Cloud System DSS inputs include all patient relevant recorded data (see Figure 15), some of which are continuously recorded, some periodically, and some when changed:

- Patient hub data (bio signals, external medical devices data).
- Clinical examination data, that show current clinical status
- Medication list, as defined by the HCP, for known adverse effects.
- Questionnaire answers and scores, for symptoms, depression, etc, that are periodically answered by patients.
- Feature extraction output (Clinical findings device assertables, e.g. coughing, tachycardia etc) as well as activity. These are outputs of the machine learning modules that are executed in the feature extraction server. These features are calculated in real time for every 5 min segment, and the produced outputs refer to detection of events of medical importance, e.g. arrhythmias, or conditions, e.g. running. It has to be noted that multichannel information is used where relevant (ECG, lung sounds), and quality filters are applied to reject low quality recordings.

These data and features are all described in the datamodel (see <http://medilomi.med.auth.gr:8000/>) and stored in the cloud storage. Details for the feature extraction have been described in D3.1, D3.2 and D5.1.

The DSS rules employed can be distinguished in two categories.

Abnormalities. The first category concerns rules that identify distinct abnormalities according to known and medically accepted thresholds, for example the threshold for high blood pressure, fever, etc (see D3.2 Appendix A Table 16, and answers to simple questions from D3.1 Appendix 5.2. The abnormalities do not necessarily point to a specific ‘diagnosed’ situation, i.e. may not be disease specific, if not combined, but highlight a change in health status. The material on thresholds and abnormalities of Deliverable D2.3 has been the basis for this category of rules, although the distinction between major and minor abnormalities was not followed, as the introduction of double thresholds was not trivial, nor was enough evidence available. Examples: “*if coughing detected then abnormal state*”, “*if body temperature > 37.9 Celsius then abnormal state*”. The WELCOME cloud infrastructure formulates the daily report regarding aggregated abnormalities observed during the

day. Visualisation of the total number of abnormalities over time, via the WELCOME applications, would then allow for visual inspection, and enable the HCP or researcher to correlate this measure of patient status with annotated events (e.g. hospitalizations or change of medications or biosignal patterns). Upon availability of data, machine learning could also allow for investigation of unknown abnormality clusters and their predictive power, potentially leading to new rules on a population or groupwise level. In summary, the abnormality aggregation strategy results in a periodic (daily) report with linked instances. The orchestrator agent once per day triggers the DSS to produce this report.

Complex Comorbidity rules. These include multiple conditions and refer more specifically to diseases, problems and causalities. The procedure through which these rules were formulated by experts is described in 2.4.1. An example is *“if activity decreasing and depression scale high, and no other vital sign change, then potential depression”*. Effort was paid to include rules that apply not only to COPD, but also to the comorbidities, as deterioration may be caused by either conditions. A measure of the rule’s certainty is the number of ‘optional’ conditions that are true in addition to the ‘mandatory’ ones.

In addition, in order to increase robustness and decrease potential alert “noise”, caused for example by biosignal artifacts, temporal aggregation is applied as a meta-rule. In this sense, a rule is fired only if its conditions are met for an adequate (predefined) number of segments. This helps for example to avoid alerts that are oversensitive to potential circumstantial errors of the feature extraction engine (i.e. detection of states), due to temporarily decreased measurement quality, and applies to conditions that are not supposed to be just momentary and then disappear, but are expected to be detected during a considerable time-frame.

The output of rules includes: a) Abnormalities detected based on the provided information. The output makes available both the aggregation of daily distinct abnormality types (e.g. 10 abnormalities today vs 8 yesterday), along with the list of daily abnormalities for further exploration, and b) Warnings for specific states based on single or combined conditions. These can be either warnings for potential adverse drug events, or for disease deterioration (Exacerbation, Pulmonary oedema, deterioration in Depression, Pulmonary embolism, Hypo/Hyperglycemia, Diabetes deregulation, Pneumonia, Cardiac arrhythmias).

This output format is provided in textual format, which includes the text message along with Rule specific content. For complex rules, the rule certainty is provided, as the number of “optional” conditions met, in addition to the mandatory ones. The optional conditions are considered as adding more confidence to the detection of a clinical condition. For traceability and justification, the rule output is linked to the facts triggering rule that can be accessed for further investigation of the situation. Details regarding the DSS functionality and the produced outcomes are presented in D5.1 and D5.2. An example textual output of firing rule w38 (also shown in D5.2):

“There are indications of possible acute exacerbation of COPD. Possible indications coming from WELCOME system:

- *Answers to questions:*
 - *Did your sputum increase today == true*
 - *What is the color of your sputum == purulent*
- *The average of baseline crackles has increased 18%*
- *Increase in mMMRC score : +2*
- *For the last 2 days the total resting activity has been 130%*
- *Heart rate average increased 20%*
- *Respiratory rate average increased 18%*
- *SpO2 average decreased 3%*

Rule’s optional conditions met: 4 out of 6”

Listing 1: DSS example text output

It has to be clarified that, at the current stage, the output of the rules is only visible via the HCP applications (WP6), and thus it is evaluated by the HCPs. No DSS rule output arrives directly to the patient apps at this stage.

<p>IF</p> <p><i>Current Diseases contains E08*-E13*</i></p> <p><i>Deviation from baseline HR >15%</i></p> <p><i>Temperature >38 C</i></p> <p><i>Deviation from baseline Blood Glucose Level > 30%</i></p> <p><i>ABS(Deviation from baseline Spo2) < 3</i></p> <p><i>Deviation from baseline respRate resting < 15%</i></p> <p><i>ABS (Deviation from baseline FEV1 (EIT)) < 3%</i></p> <p><i>ABS(Deviation from baseline IVC (EIT)) < 5%</i></p> <p>THEN</p> <p><i>Alert Diabetologist/ Possible diabetes deregulation</i></p> <p><i>Alert patient for more frequent temperature measurements / possible infection</i></p> <p><i>Alert patient for more frequent Blood Glucose measurements</i></p>	<p>IF</p> <p><i>Current Diseases contains J44*</i></p> <p><i>Did your sputum increase today == true</i></p> <p><i>What is the color of your sputum == purulent</i></p> <p><i>Deviation from baseline crackles > 15%</i></p> <p><i>mMMRC change > 0 (1-->2,2-->3, etc)</i></p> <p><i>OPTIONAL Last 2 days (Total Resting Activity > 120% baseline)</i></p> <p><i>OPTIONAL Deviation from baseline HR resting > 15%</i></p> <p>THEN</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>1. Possible Acute Exacerbation of COPD</i> <i>2. Prompt patient to increase dosage of rescue inhaler</i> <i>3. Prompt patient to contact pulmonologist/GP</i>
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Figure 16: a) Increase of heart rate, temperature and glucose, without pneumonology related findings in a patient with COPD and diabetes comorbidity are suggesting a deregulation of origin different than COPD, i.e. potential diabetes deregulation or infection. b) In this case, the combination of conditions suggests that the COPD worsening is possible, and the certainty is increased if the optional conditions are met, provided that the biosignal related conditions are met for more than 30' continuously.

2.4.1 Welcome DSS Complex Rules Development and the clinical perspective

The creation of the complex clinical rules for the WELCOME Medical Decision Support System (DSS) was based on the scarce existing literature about home monitoring of COPD patients in conjunction with a consensus between clinical experts from the fields of Pulmonology and the specialties involved in the studied comorbidities. The methodology consisted of reviewing the current medical literature and then exploring patient specific case studies of COPD patients under supervision from the clinical settings involved in the WELCOME project. At a third stage, these case studies were analyzed and a panel of medical and technical experts was formed in order to propose a set of complex rules for diagnosis and evaluation of the severity of the diseases under study. The produced list of candidate

rules was further refined and reviewed by the rest of the medical experts in the five clinical sites that participate in the clinical validation of the WELCOME system and a final set of DSS rules was created. The informatics experts were provided with this set and incorporated the rules in the context of the medical DSS of the proposed system.

As concerns the first stage of the aforementioned process, the literature search aimed in finding the existing knowledge about the proper monitoring of COPD patients at a stable disease stage as well as before or during acute exacerbation episodes. At the same time we tried to explore whether there are any published results about methods of patients' follow up able to predict upcoming exacerbations. The use of keywords for the literature search was mandatory and the terms used for the search included the words: COPD exacerbation prediction, AE-COPD, follow up of COPD patients, COPD disease severity assessment or evaluation, COPD disease progression, home care or home monitoring or remote monitoring for COPD patients. The results based on internet search showed several articles and guidelines describing the staging and follow up of COPD patients but no sound methodology for close monitoring of the disease progression from remote locations, especially when it comes to valid prediction of upcoming exacerbation events. Naturally, the GOLD committee report (at its current 2017 update) [1] has incorporated and analyzed all the existing literature about monitoring and follow up of stable COPD patients and thus served as a primary guide for the existing knowledge on the field. Overall, there are no specific guidelines for the remote monitoring of the COPD patients. Instead, one can find certain rules for assessing COPD, the pulmonary function and the existing comorbidities, with the intention to assess the overall health status and prevent exacerbations.

Secondly, in view of the experience gathered at the five medical centers supporting the clinical trials of WELCOME project, we tried to track real life case scenarios from patients under supervision at these sites. The data from the patients' follow up were collected and related to potential disease exacerbations noticed in their medical history. The pulmonologists from the clinical settings commented on the most frequent symptoms (subjective and objective signs) experienced by their patients preceding an acute exacerbation and provided input in the form of case studies, like the ones found in Appendix A.

The next step involved the forming of a consensus committee in Greece, which served as a panel of experts in managing COPD patients, able to describe and refine complex decision rules for the remote management of the disease and its comorbid conditions. The experts involved were two pulmonologists-intensivists, a cardiologist, an internal medicine specialist and a psychiatrist, in order to cover all the comorbidities under study in WELCOME. The experts had a close understanding of medical informatics and have been conducting research with the lab of medical informatics (Medical School of Thessaloniki, Greece) for the last years. The panel was completed by two experts in medical informatics with previous experience in development of decision support systems. This was deemed necessary in order to facilitate the smooth adaptation of the created natural language rules into the format of the programming environment of the DSS. The task undertaken by the committee was the consideration of the related literature and the formation of simple and more complex clinical decision rules that are able to distinguish among different alterations of the health status of the COPD patients [2], taking into account the special characteristics of those suffering from known comorbidities [3]. The produced rules were able either to help in categorizing the patients into formal groups of COPD severity or stage (according to the existing universally acceptable GOLD guidelines [1] – example 1), or determine whether there is an increased risk of a destabilization of the disease equilibrium in the form of an acute exacerbation of any of the comorbid diagnosed conditions [4] (examples 2 & 3).

w13	GOLD STAGE>=3	No of exacerbations during last 12months>=2	CAT Score>=10		GOLD Patient Group=>D
w14	GOLD STAGE>=3	No of exacerbations during last 12months>=2	mMRC Score>=2		GOLD Patient Group=>D

Figure 17: Example Rule 1

w28	Deviation from baseline respRate non-resting>15%	Deviation from baseline HR non-resting>15%	Deviation from baseline Spo2 non-resting <= -3	non-resting tachycardia=1	Deviation from baseline no. of cough episodes>15%	Temperature >37	Deviation from baseline FEV1 (EIT)<-3%
	ABS(Deviation from baseline IVC (EIT))<3%	Deviation from baseline crackles>15%	Deviation from baseline wheezing expiratory>15%	Deviation mMRC from previous >0	Did your sputum increase today=yes	What is the color of your sputum=purulent	Risk of Acute infectious exacerbation of COPD: Contact your Doctor, if symptoms persist visit

Figure 18: Example Rule 2

w39	Current Diseases contains E08*-E13*	Blood Glucose Level < 40 (mg/dL)	Deviation from baseline activity resting > 20%	Temperature <36 C	Sinus Tachycardia	Tachypnea	ABS(Deviation from baseline IVC (EIT))<3%	lung sounds no change	1. Possible hypoglycemia 2. Prompt Carer/patient to give patient glucose/sweets 3. Alert diabetologist
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Figure 19: Example Rule 3

The experts tried to blend their own expertise in treating patients with COPD and its comorbid conditions together with the recommendations given for monitoring stable COPD patients [1,2,5]. In addition, they tried to include assessment items in the form of answers to questionnaires given by the patients themselves as well as objective measurements obtained by the sensors of the vest or the interconnected devices. These assessment items will serve as input to known COPD assessment tools capable of evaluating the exacerbation risk or the long term mortality from the disease, like the EXACT tool [6] or the BODE index [7]. It should be stated at this point that real life data from patients monitored at home for a long period of time before an acute exacerbation or a comorbid disease deregulation are lacking from current body of evidence and therefore the authors of the DSS rules were obliged to make assumptions on the validity of proposed predictors of disease deteriorations. These assumptions were of course based on clinical expertise and experience and will definitely be tested and validated in the pilot clinical trials of the WELCOME system as a whole. This will lead to modifications of the preliminary thresholds set and even the context of certain rules that will prove inefficient in capturing the real extend of the disease burden in the test subjects. Currently, the evaluation of the health status and the firing procedure of the produced rules are based on the notion of the rolling average of baseline measurements for every individual patient, in order for the system to be more personalized and effective in assessing different sets of comorbid abnormalities. This rolling average will be automatically calculated by the system at each given point of time based on the measurements of the preceding days prior to a disease progression (comparison of the present bioparameter value to an average one from the preceding days). This way, the system will take into account the day to day variability that has been described in the typical COPD patients [1,2,4], avoiding false positive alerts.

The total volume of the DSS rules developed covers many areas of interest in the management of COPD and its comorbidities, like presentation of subjective symptoms, exercise tolerance, sleep quality, quality of life, drug interactions and adverse effects, emergency situations and alerts and classification of the present diseases. The rules were modified to fit in the format of the DSS under development by the IT experts of the panel.

The rule set was then shared with the rest of the medical experts participating in the WELCOME project for internal validation, comments and amendments. The healthcare professionals from four

European countries carefully examined the produces rules and made suggestions on clarifications and enhancements on certain occasions. The resulting set of complex rules was created and circulated among the consortium partners before the final implementation to the DSS of the system. D3.2 presents a summarized view of the rules.

The WELCOME development strategy for a successful launch of the system in the market considering the aforementioned aspects from step 1 of the project to an operational prototype considering relevant HL7 FHIR version as well as standards and directives to prepare for a potential Medical Device CE.

2.5 Strategy regarding the WELCOME data-model maintenance and HL7 FHIR adoption

The WELCOME cloud data storage service, namely WELCOME communication API and WELCOME Storage Engine data model are designed with three main objectives: flexibility, scalability and interoperability.

Interoperability is facilitated through the adoption of the Linked Data principles and the early adoption of HL7 FHIR. Scalability and flexibility are facilitated by the fact that new resources can easily be added to the model without changing the WELCOME communication API endpoints. Flexibility regarding updates is facilitated through keeping a **single point of change**, namely the WELCOME ontology, as it defines the data model and the WELCOME communication API endpoints. In case of an update, the WELCOME endpoints are automatically updated to be compatible with the project’s data model [15].

The WELCOME consortium adopted HL7 FHIR from its early days and invested heavily on transforming it in an RDF based model. The decision to build upon HL7 FHIR was presented in D3.2 section 4.2.1.1, to summarize, was based mainly on the open nature of the standard¹⁰ and the status that HL7 has among health related standards. After several months, HL7 FHIR started publishing a version of RDF representation. This is ongoing work and id annotated with the following hint: “*RDF forms are particularly prone to change. The page is not part of the current ballot, and so at the most it can be a draft page in DSTU 2*”¹¹. Table 7 compares the two RDF representations, WELCOME ontology and HL7 online RDF representation in N-triples format using the basic “Patient” entity as an example, depicting that the rationale of the RDF representation is very similar. Moreover, as a confirmation of the WELCOME ontology rationale’s validity, our approach has been published as an HL7 FHIR based ontology for telehealth in the HL7 Newsletter in the September 2016 issue¹².

Table 7: Comparison between HL7 and WELCOME RDF representation

WELCOME Data model	HL7 RDF representation
--------------------	------------------------

¹⁰ “FHIR is licensed under Creative Commons “No Rights Reserved”, and states that “You can create derivative specifications or implementation-related products and services” (<https://www.hl7.org/fhir/license.html>) and Why FHIR is better “Specification is free for use with no restrictions” in <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/summary.html>

¹¹ <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/rdf.html> (accessed Nov 2016)

¹² http://www.hl7.org/documentcenter/public_temp_529761BE-1C23-BA17-0C5A0D7857F8A720/newsletters/HL7_NEWS_20160913.pdf

<pre> :Patient_1 a :Patient ; :Person.name [a FHIRct:HumanName ; FHIRct:HumanName.text [A FHIRpt:string ; rdf:value "John Smith"^^xsd:string]] . </pre>	<pre> :Patient_1 a fhir:Patient; fhir:Patient.name [fhir:text [fhir:string.value "John Smith"]] . </pre>
---	---

Considering the maturity level of the RDF representation of HL7 FHIR, the standard will continue to evolve this representation almost certainly even after the end of WELCOME project. Also, new HL7 FHIR versions introduced usually include additions of resources and less frequently minor changes to existing resources. Therefore, we consider safe to assume that major changes to the already defined data entities will not be a major problem and will not have a heavy impact on our semantic or syntactic compatibility with HL7 FHIR.

Moreover, since WELCOME data model is not only a conceptual model but also an operational one as it is used to define the WELCOME communication API endpoints, we have to define a stabilization point in order to facilitate the development of the WELCOME cloud infrastructure client applications. It should be noted that according to HL7, *"FHIR is licensed under Creative Commons "No Rights Reserved", and states that "You can create derivative specifications or implementation-related products and services"*¹³ so we based our system development on DSTU2 ballot, 0.5.0.

In order to facilitate future updates in the model (either required to be compatible with HL7 FHIR or if needed by WELCOME's applications), we have defined a process which is backwards compatible with minimal maintenance effort. Backwards compatibility is important because such an update would not require an update on the client applications. Figure 20 provides a diagram of the overall process.

¹³ <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/license.html>

Figure 20: The WELCOME data model operational update cycle

According to our data model update process, the data model developer may alter the WELCOME ontology and the WELCOME communication API is automatically updated with new endpoints that handle (accept, modify, delete) the aforementioned resource. For example, if WELCOME decides that there is a need for storing information about Person groups then the introduction of the HL7 FHIR resource “Group”¹⁴ would seem suitable. The data model developer would have to add the resource in the corresponding position in the ontology tree creating and assigning the corresponding properties. Once the new ontology is updated on the cloud server the communication API will enable the management of this type of resources by the clients after a simple restart without any further code modifications or module rebuilds, therefore minimizing required maintenance effort.

Updating existing resources (e.g. the change in the name of a resource – from QuestionnaireAnswers to QuestionnaireResponses¹⁵) – would typically require severe manual work in several development levels to be incorporated in most of the current data management systems, especially after having actual data existing on the data storage. Renaming a data model entity would typically require each client application to review, rebuild and redeploy all the modules that use the specific entity. Furthermore, if data are already stored they must be manually replaced by data pointing on the new entity, a procedure which is very error prone.

The WELCOME data services leverage the tools provided by the standard OWL semantics, namely the owl:equivalentClass and owl:sameAs property, to overcome such an issue and keep backwards

¹⁴ Group: Represents a defined collection of entities that may be discussed or acted upon collectively but which are not expected to act collectively and are not formally or legally recognized; i.e. a collection of entities that isn't an Organization.(<http://hl7.org/fhir/group.html>)

¹⁵ This is an actual change made from DSTU2 ballot 0.5.0 to DSTU2

compatibility without enforcing imminent change to the client applications. We can add the new resource with the new name and as described above automatically any client could use the new resource version. In addition, we could use semantic annotations that describe that the new resource refers the same entity as the pre-existing. This annotation consists of two triples in the ontology using owl:equivalentClass and owl:sameAs¹⁶ property

```
:QuestionnaireAnswers owl:sameAs :QuestionnaireResponses;
```

```
:QuestionnaireAnswers owl:equivalentClass :QuestionnaireResponses;
```

Having this annotation and using a reasoner the system would infer that the two OWL classes refer to the same concept and they have the exact same individuals and return data from instances of both resources when a client requests data about either of them¹⁷.

It must be stated that HL7 FHIR is a still evolving standard and it is out of the scope of this project to be in complete accordance with any FHIR published version. Nonetheless, during the development of the system's prototype minor evolutions to the data model were introduced based on the needs of the WELCOME applications, during those changes new properties defined by FHIR that were relevant to WELCOME were incorporated to WELCOME ontology.

Finally, in order to facilitate the WELCOME ontology's development, review and possible future refactoring, we have deployed several knowledge engineering tools. The WELCOME ontology may be accessed online¹⁸ either for reuse or for review purposes. The ontology is open for import by other projects¹⁹ and we also host a visualization of the ontology using WebVOWL²⁰ (also free to online access²¹ <http://medilomi.med.auth.gr:8000/>), a snapshot of which is shown in Figure 21.

¹⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/owl-ref/>

¹⁷ The functionality described is not currently implemented by the communication API since it is not required for the scope of the project.

¹⁸ http://lomi.med.auth.gr/ontologies/WELCOME_entities

¹⁹ The published part of the ontology (FHIR Primitive and FHIR Complex types ontologies were made available to a researcher in US upon request)

²⁰ Lohmann, S.; Link, V.; Marbach, E.; Negru, S.: WebVOWL: Web-Based Visualization of Ontologies. Proceedings of EKAW 2014 Satellite Events, LNAI 8982, pp. 154-158, Springer, 2015. [BibTex]

²¹ <http://medilomi.med.auth.gr:8000/>

Figure 21: WELCOME Entities ontology visualization part

3 Design lifecycle

In this section, the WELCOME software's design lifecycle is being described. It should be noted that while the design overlaps with the development of the system, the development process per se is considered out of the current document's scope and that the design lifecycle refers to the WELCOME project's software (does not refer to the development of the vest).

3.1 Rationale

The consortium committed on a standard-based management design and development of the system from the first project's phase [16]. In this section, we provide a rationale on the selection and adoption and a brief overview of the respective standards, regarding the project's design process.

The key factors differentiating WELCOME compared to a typical telematics project considered during the WELCOME's design phase are:

1. Distributed consortium

The WELCOME project consortium consists of many organizations (companies, universities, health care providers) distributed across Europe. These organizations have different background, expertise, work methodologies and goals. While this synthesis is invaluable in terms of advancing research, it also hinders the establishment of a strict work methodology, having profound impact on the project's design lifecycle.

2. Safety as priority

As in every medical IT system, even in research projects, the safety of the patients is the first priority for WELCOME. Therefore, the need of a specific risk management process has been identified in order to ensure patient safety and the overall system's quality.

3. Need for standards

Following standardized procedures is a crucial feature facilitating future product certifications and assuring the overall quality of the produced outcome.

These key factors defined the project's design and development methodology and the use of the respective standards that the process is based on.

The WELCOME's design lifecycle is based on two standards, namely IEC 62304 (Medical device software — Software life cycle processes) [10] and ISO 14971 (Medical devices — Application of risk management to medical devices) [11], adapting the standards guidelines to the consortium's and the project's needs. Both above standards provide guidance on managing the risks and the design/development lifecycle of the system, while also allowing the flexibility to adjust the suggested processes²², key feature for distributed teams like the WELCOME consortium's team. The conformance/compliance to the standard is left to be confirmed by a specific auditing mechanism, which would certify if the specific process is compliant with the standard. The WELCOME consortium

²² For example, in the IEC 62304 compliance section, it is explicitly stated that "Although the specified processes, activities, and tasks are performed, flexibility exists in the methods of implementing these processes and performing these activities and tasks."

has clearly decided to avoid any kind of certification process as it is considered out of the project's scope. It is understood that such certifications could be necessary for a product development, which is one of the project's possible future pathways, however the cost of certification process (both in money and time) inevitably sets them out of the project's scope. However, following the respective standards without pursuing a certification allowed the project to stay compatible with project's time schedule and budget, while also keeping its future marketing options as the certification procedures would easily be applied in a possible product development process.

3.1.1 IEC 62304

The IEC 62304 standard defines a software lifecycle process to be followed when designing and developing medical software. It provides a framework of life cycle *processes*, *activities* and *tasks* organized as shown in Figure 22 [10], under which the specific design/development process should be organized, following the respective instructions or requirements imposed by the standard. It should be noted that IEC 62304 refers to ISO 14971 as a prerequisite. It should be clarified that only the acting to the design of the system are considered in scope for the current document.

Figure 22: IEC 62304 overview of processes and activities [10]

3.1.2 ISO 14971

The ISO 14971 defines a framework for the systematic risk management on the development and use of medical devices. The standard provides a definition of specific terminology used in such processes and suggests methods to initially quantify and finally minimize the risks of the device usage. The risk management process as defined in the ISO 14971 is shown in Figure 23 [11].

Figure 23: ISO 14971 schematic representation of the risk management process [4]

Two key-points of ISO 14971's rationale are the following:

1. The concept of *risk* is defined as follows: *"It is accepted that the concept of risk has two components: a) the probability of occurrence of harm; b) the consequences of that harm, that is, how severe it might be."*
2. While the above definition of risk is clearly based on the quantification of the risk's probability of occurrence, it is clear that this should not prevent decision making: *"The decision to use a medical device in the context of a particular clinical procedure requires the residual risks to be balanced against the anticipated benefits of the procedure"*. Therefore, even if the residual risk of a specific procedure cannot be credibly quantified, the procedure should still be applied if we are certain that the benefit of the procedure is bigger than the risk.

3.2 WELCOME design lifecycle

Given the technical challenges of the proposed system, the complexity of the proposal's clinical context and the difficulty of distributed teams management, the consortium followed a design lifecycle the main features of which directly correspond to the main characteristics of the WELCOME project and can be summarized as follows:

1. Agility

Following the widely used modern agile methodologies, the design process is based on frequent direct communication between the project's stakeholders (health care professionals, technical team, management) rather than maintaining hard to follow strict time tables and heavy documentation. Such collaboration methodologies during the design of a system, are commonly referred with the term **Joint Application Design (JAD)** [12]. JAD is an adaptive approach that enables the quick dissemination and the immediate response to issues that come up (e.g. technical difficulties), exploiting feedback from the ongoing development of the system. Therefore, frequent teleconferences between the teams participating in each Work Package (WP) or even among the WPs have been conducted, in order to promote the active participation of all the stakeholders and facilitate the cooperation among remote teams. These teleconferences followed a relaxed iterative approach (typically every two weeks) while also encouraging ad-hoc communication whenever needed. When necessary, technical face-to-face meetings have been arranged in order to facilitate the communication between technical teams.

2. Risk management

As risk management has been identified as a priority, the consortium decided that it should be guided by a standardized process, namely the ISO 14971 defined principles. Therefore, the WELCOME's design process engaged ISO 14971 by maintaining a centralized and updated Risk Management File which clearly defines the consortium's risk management policy. Furthermore, a central risk management table exists on each of the project's deliverables, following the principles defined in the standard. The risks identified during this process defined the consortiums design decisions and heavily influenced the overall development of the project, as specific tests and mitigation strategies have been implemented and acted upon.

3. Standard based design process

The WELCOME project's design process has not only used ISO 14971 in order to ensure quality for risk management process, but has also adopted IEC 62304 to define the main design activities needed. IEC 62394 defined design activities heavily influenced the design lifecycle of the system on short-term iterations as well as long-term design milestones too. The IEC 62394 activities considered as part of the WELCOME project's design methodology are development planning, requirements analysis, architectural design and detailed design. These four activities have been part of every iterative design phase (short-term) and have been extensively elaborated in the two main project's design milestones, the deliverables 3.1 and 3.2 (long-term).

Figure 24 depicts the evolution of the WELCOME's design lifecycle rationale, some of the key design milestones, as well as the impact of the development process' feedback to the design of the system.

Figure 24: Design lifecycle overview

Following the described design lifecycle has two main benefits, especially regarding a possible future product development as a result of WELCOME project:

1. The agile JAD oriented work methodology has allowed the consortium to interact efficiently, following a widely-adopted product management approach. This approach has successfully led to quick mitigation of risks and adjustments of the design and development plans. Furthermore, it helped the consortium to identify each team’s special characteristics and establish the required project management mechanisms, necessary for a possible future product development.
2. The standard oriented design and risk management approach improved the overall quality of the produced system (e.g. facilitated in-time risk identification and mitigation). Moreover, in a possible future product outcome, this process could provide valuable input and experience to certification processes (e.g. CE marking) and can therefore be considered as a preparatory step.

The main design activities defined as part of the IEC 62304 standard (Figure 22) and the use of ISO 14971 are the main activities around which the WELCOME project’s design evolved. Therefore, the rest of the section describes how these activities evolved and their significant contribution to the overall design, using specific design aspects of the WELCOME system as an example.

3.3 Software development planning

Software development planning refers not only to the long-term definition of milestones and time schedules, but also on the short-term performed actions. Regarding the long-term development planning, the consortium has committed on the milestones defined in the Description of Work (DoW) document. The short-term software development planning took place during the iterative teleconferences, where each time undertook specific tasks and informed the rest about the progress of the undergoing work.

The WELCOME project’s software platform consist of many independent modules interconnected through well defined software interfaces. Typically, each module has been assigned to one of the

consortium members which worked independently. In the iterative teleconferences, the issues regarding the interconnection of the modules and “vertical” issues regarding the integrated emerging functionality have been discussed. Most of the work regarding the independent modules per se has been planned as each partner’s internal work. This approach allowed us to reduce the communication cost, while still maintaining a (JAD) approach.

For example, while the WELCOME Cloud communication API required large amount of effort and this has been considered mainly work of the AUTH team. However, since the communication API is to be used by other modules, namely the patient hub and the WELCOME applications, the overall rationale of communication and the signature of the respective endpoints has been extensively defined among the partners, process that led to two well defined and documented versions of the communications API.

This agile software development planning process, combined with the risk mitigation process, has also led to successful mitigation of major risks. For example, the implementation of an algorithm reconstructing EIT images from raw EIT data has been identified as a gap in the planning of the project. Therefore, the implementation of the specific algorithm has been assigned to the AUTH team and the risk has been successfully mitigated.

Evaluating the software development planning procedure we can safely conclude that it has been successful since no major delays regarding software development existed and risks have been mitigated. On the contrary, the consortium demonstrated a system prototype engaging all the main functionality, sooner than expected, namely on the second year’s review (month 27 instead of month 30).

3.4 Software requirements analysis

WELCOME project’s DoW defined the task “Requirements and features analysis” planned as part of WP2. During this task, several focus groups and interviews have been conducted, targeting patients and their informal carers, as well as health care professionals. The outcome of this process has been passed as input to the WP3 to refine them and use them as the basis of shaping the formal requirements to be satisfied by the WELCOME system.

The consortium early identified the complexity of the system and the need to consider the impact on patients’ real-life scenarios and the clinical context during the requirements analysis process. Therefore, the first step of the process was to identify a list of “business processes” with which the designed system would interact, based on the input of the WP2, namely the analysis of the contacted focus groups and the clinical models applied on the participating countries where the clinical trials will be conducted. These “business processes” refer to real-life processes (e.g. clinical care processes, typical patient life-style activities etc.) on which the WELCOME system would be engaged and have been explicitly defined in the D3.1 and updated in the D3.2.

The requirements list has been based on the “business processes” list and has been defined in D3.1 and revised in D3.2. The updates of the requirements have been an integral part of the iteration design process, improving as the design details were clarified. It should be noted that each one of the requirements would be related with either a defined “business process” or an explicitly stated requirement defined in the WP2 outcomes. This facilitates tracking each requirement’s origin, to verify its implementation in the system or further elaborate on it. Finally, based on the detailed requirements list, several use case diagrams have been created to further clarify the required functionality and the respective user roles.

The overall requirements evolved through several teleconferences and face-to-face meetings, following the so-called **Joint Requirements Development (JRD) sessions** [13] paradigm. In these meetings, all consortium's stakeholders contributed as the requirements usually have "vertical" (cross-functional) implications that could be missed in the user interviews process or could be ignored by individual stakeholders focusing on specific parts of design and implementation.

3.5 Software architectural design

The consortium quickly identified the importance of designing the WELCOME system using a modularized and highly compartmentalized architecture, defining distinct modules and clean stable communication interfaces among them. Designing in various levels is a common software engineering practice [14] in order to minimize interdependencies between modules and risks regarding their development.

The architecture of the system can be considered on two levels, top-level and low-level architecture details:

- The top-level architecture defined the major modules of the system and their interconnection interfaces and once decided did not evolve significantly.
- The low-level architecture refers to the internal architecture of each module and this evolved during the whole design phase as feedback was provided by the first working prototypes.

The above two levels architectural design process approach proved to be very efficient as it clearly defined the limits of the modules to be developed by each team, while still providing them the necessary flexibility to modify their internal architecture in an agile fashion.

For example, the Feature Extraction Server (FES), namely the module which extracts high level features from biosignals' raw data, wraps the algorithms used in a Matlab runtime (low-level architecture) and exposes them through a web services interface (top-level architecture). This design proved to be very efficient for rapid deployment in a research context, as signal processing algorithms continuously updated and are deployed in the environment they are typically written and tested (Matlab). However, in a future product environment with high throughput needs, the FES algorithms would typically be written in another programming language and perhaps alter the scheme of distributing the requests for performance reasons. The architectural choice of defining a top-level steady architecture, namely the web services interface, allows altering the internal FES architectural decision improving the FES performance without affecting the modules interacting with it.

Moreover, this two-level separation of architecture design facilitates the exploitation of the various modules in future possible product pathways. For example, the FES could be exploitable following the service oriented approach, independently of the rest of the WELCOME system's features, exploiting the respective top-level design choice to be interfaced as a group of web service endpoints. Another example, would be the WELCOME Storage Engine CRUD application stack which has been developed internally as a layered scaffolding framework (low-level architecture design), being able to support other data models, just by changing the respective data model ontology [15].

Technically, the architecture of the system has been heavily influenced by the micro-services and the multi-tier design patterns. For example, while the WELCOME FES is deployed as a set of web services endpoints, typically called by the Orchestrator Agent (OA), the OA itself is a layer in the overall WELCOME cloud services infrastructure, also containing other layers itself.

3.6 Software detailed design

Following the rationale of the overall design methodology, the detailed design of the various software modules has been conducted by the teams that these modules have been assigned to. The teleconferences conducted have proved extremely useful in order to clarify details and communicate the details of each module between the various stakeholders.

A number of design tools have been engaged in the detailed design of the respective modules, used according to the needs and the expertise of each team, as well as the specific needs of communication among them.

- *Class diagrams*

Class diagrams have been used to clarify the structure of the various applications (e.g. patient hub applications).

- *Sequence diagrams*

Sequence diagrams have been used to define the communication processes between the various modules of the system.

- *Entity-relationship diagrams*

Entity-relationship diagrams have been used to define the data structure of relational-like databases (e.g. patient hub applications local storage)

- *Use case diagrams*

Use case diagrams have been used to clarify the needed functionality of the WELCOME modules based on the detailed requirements list.

- *Long term maintained documents in a shareable workspace (sharepoint)*

In order to define details which would evolve over time, a number of documents have been created and shared between the consortium through a common shared web workspace. These documents have been frequently updated by the specific cross-partners team members in order to synchronize their design efforts. Examples of such design activities include the exact definition of the FES endpoints, the DSS rules, the core data model entities etc.

3.7 Risk management

The WELCOME project's design process has included constant risk management procedures which are based on the guidelines of ISO 14971, as it has been reported in D1.1 and D1.3. Furthermore, ISO 14971 describes rigorous procedures which could be adapted to the respective project's workflow. There are two ISO 14971 key requirements that have been adopted in the project's design phase:

1. The classification of the respective medical device

The consortium investigated the classification of the WELCOME software stack and decided that it is of Class IIa according to EU's Directive 93/42/EEC.

2. The main requirement is the maintenance of one central document, the Risk Management File, where the risks are documented, quantified and mitigation steps are recorded.

The project's Risk Management File is kept as an internal (non-public) document and is iteratively reviewed and updated. Furthermore, a table of risks has been presented in each design and development deliverable (e.g. D3.1 and D3.2) and has guided the design process as safety is one of the project's priorities. The current snapshot of the risk table can be found in the document attached to the current deliverable document as part B (also referenced in Appendix C).

As a proof of its successful implementation and the added value that the specific risk management activity we can give several examples. For instance, the consortium very early identified the risk of implementing the feature extraction algorithms without having real data, while the vest was under development. Therefore, data have been collected from the COIMBRA and AUTH team in order to facilitate the respective algorithm's development. Furthermore, sample file signals have been created in order to use them in the overall project's software stack testing, without waiting for a vest to produce them.

Following the ISO 14971 is a preparatory step for a possible future product approach, as it is a prerequisite for ISO 13485, typically a prerequisite for the CE marking of a product. Therefore, we can safely conclude that the WELCOME consortium's risk management approach would facilitate a possible future product pathway.

4 Steps towards CE marking

In this section, we provide a brief overview of the CE marking procedure and then a scenario of applying the CE marking process to the WELCOME software system. The medical sensors employed are already certified, while the hardware considerations, i.e. the wearable vest related documentation is addressed in WP4. This scenario walkthrough would verify the maturity of the followed design and development process while also indicating the steps to be followed in a future product pathway. As WELCOME software system certification is not a trivial task, the consortium is in contact with experts in the field, NATIONAL EVALUATION CENTER OF QUALITY AND TECHNOLOGY IN HEALTH S.A.- EKAPTY, Smyrnis 15, 165 62 GLYFADA, Athens, to seek further guidance, in case an opportunity for CE certification comes forth soon after the end of the project.

4.1 CE marking process

CE marking is used throughout the European Economic Area (EEA) to declare that the manufacturer of a product explicitly states that the product meets the safety, health and environmental protection requirements set by the EU, and it applies not only to medical devices but all marketable products.

It should be noted that the compliance of product with the actual requirements is left to the manufacturer, who *“assumes full responsibility for its compliance with all safety requirements”*²³. Therefore, CE marking is not a guarantee and should not be confused with a safety certification.

Typically, a manufacturer would have to implement a six-steps procedure to affix a CE marking to the respective product²⁴:

1. Identify the applicable directive(s) and harmonized standards
2. Verify product specific requirements
3. Identify whether an independent conformity assessment (by a notified body) is necessary
4. Test the product and check its conformity
5. Draw up and keep available the required technical documentation
6. Affix the CE marking and draw up the EU Declaration of Conformity

Details regarding the above six steps are considered out of the current document’s scope. However, it should be noted that the first step of the process is the most critical one, as steps 2, 3, 4 and 5 would typically be applied against the standards identified in step 1.

4.2 Application of CE Marking to the WELCOME software stack

Even though CE marking is not a prerequisite or a guarantee for the WELCOME software system’s (or the possible future products originating from WELCOME project), it can be considered a typical pathway to market and therefore a process to be aligned with.

²³ https://ec.europa.eu/growth/single-market/ce-marking/consumers_en

²⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/growth/single-market/ce-marking/manufacturers_en

Applying a CE marking process requires defining a product and its specific use cases. Developing a product is clearly out of the WELCOME project's scope, however in this section we present a hypothetical scenario of possible future exploitation of the WELCOME project's software stack in the form of a product. In this scenario, the "WELCOME software platform" (namely the mobile applications, the web applications and the cloud platform)²⁵ would be marketed as a product with these key features:

1. It would typically target COPD patients with comorbidities
2. It would work with multiple sensors available in the market through a variety of communication interfaces
3. It would follow the "Software As A Service" (SaaS) marketing paradigm

In the rest of the section, a pathway through the six steps required for CE marking for the "WELCOME software platform" is presented. The WELCOME consortium is fully aware that such a pathway would probably require expertise regarding standardization procedures. This "vertically" applied expertise would be gained using an external agency's consulting services.

1. *Identify the applicable directive(s) and harmonized standards*

Standards IEC 62304 and ISO 14971, have been taken into account and heavily influenced the design and the development lifecycle of the platform. EU General Data Protection regulation and directives 2002/58 and 95/46/EC and ISO 18308:2011 have also been carefully revised and taken into account during the requirements' analysis of the platform [15], [16]. Moreover, Directive 93/42/EEC has been taken into account in order to classify the produced system as a Medical Device of Class IIa.

ISO 13485 (Medical devices -- Quality management systems -- Requirements for regulatory purposes) would be typically applied to a product development path. ISO 13485 is strongly related with ISO 14971 and therefore we consider that the WELCOME project has already completed a big part of step 1 required for CE marking process.

2. *Verify product specific requirements*

EU General Data Protection regulation and directives 2002/58 and 95/46/EC and ISO 18308:2011 have been carefully revised during the requirements' analysis of the platform and the final requirements' list references the respective standards extensively [15], [16].

3. *Identify whether an independent conformity assessment (by a notified body) is necessary*

Directive 93/42/EEC defines that since the WELCOME software platform is classified as Class IIa, the conformity assessment must be confirmed by a Notified Body (NB). The NB is an authority appointed by the Member States²⁶ and must be defined according to the overall marketing policy (which country will be the first that product will be sold in). Therefore, we can safely conclude that the necessary preparatory actions considered in WELCOME project's scope, have been conducted.

²⁵ The WELCOME vest is excluded from the "product" presented here as it should follow another certification pathway by itself.

²⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/growth/single-market/ce-marking/manufacturers_en

4. Test the product and check its conformity

This step could not be done without the guidance of the NB, identified in step 3 of the CE marking process. Regarding the product’s conformity check, Directive 93/42/EEC²⁷ explicitly declares two key points:

1. *“for devices which incorporate software or which are medical software in themselves, the software must be validated according to the state of the art taking into account the principles of development lifecycle, risk management, validation and verification”,* referencing directly to the respective standards engaged in the software development and maintenance lifecycle.
2. *“In the case of devices falling within Class IIa, ..., the manufacturer shall, ..., follow the procedure relating to the EC declaration of conformity set out in Annex VII, coupled with either:*
 - (a) the procedure relating to the EC verification set out in Annex IV;*
 - or*
 - (b) the procedure relating to the EC declaration of conformity set out in Annex V (production quality assurance);*
 - or*
 - (c) the procedure relating to the EC declaration of conformity set out in Annex VI (product quality assurance).”*

Regarding the first key point, the tests described in the software development deliverables, which directly correspond to risk management activities and requirements related with the standards identified in step 2 would be part of the product’s conformity check. Many such tests have already been completed and new ones are currently under development (details depicted in D5.1 and D5.2 [17]).

Regarding the second key point, the exact annexes to be followed are to be defined by the NB identified in step 3. According to the directive, activities described in Annex VII are certainly to be included, while the activities described in the rest of the annexes will be under future consideration, following the NB’s instructions. The main requirement of Annex VII is the declaration of conformity by the NB (out of WELCOME project’s scope) and the technical documentation including specific activities defined in annex’s section 3. Finally, a post-production surveillance procedure should be established (also considered out of WELCOME project’s scope). The activities described in Annex VII and their status regarding the WELCOME project are shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Annex VII conformity activities status in WELCOME project

Item	Status
Declaration of conformity	Out of project’s scope

²⁷ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CONSLEG:1993L0042:20071011:en:PDF>

Technical document:	Partially done
General description and intended use	Yes (details in D3.1 and D3.2)
Design Drawings and diagrams	Yes (details in D3.1 and D3.2)
Methods of manufacture envisaged	Yes (details in D3.1 and D3.2)
Descriptions and explanations to understand the drawings and diagrams	Yes (details in D3.1 and D3.2)
Results of the risk analysis	Yes (details in D3.1, D3.2, D5.1 and D5.2)
List of standards	Yes (D3.1, D3.2, current document)
Solutions adopted to meet the he ER	Yes (details in D3.1, D3.2, D5.1 and D5.2)
Results of design calculations and of the inspections carried out	Partially yes (details in D3.1, D3.2, D5.1 and D5.2). The inspections are to be done with the help of the NB identified in step 3.
Solutions adopted as referred to in Annex I, Chapter I, Section 2	Yes (details in D3.1, D3.2, D5.1 and D5.2)
Pre-clinical evaluation	Partially yes, through a number of software unit and integration test.
Clinical evaluation	Not yet, but the clinical trials and the “Work Package 8: Verification and Validation” designed as part of the project are a crucial part of the software platform’s verification process and they will produce solid evidence used in this step of the CE marking process
Label and instruction for use	Partially yes. The independent services developed have been documented to guide the team members building the respective client applications. The user interface applications are to be documented as part of the project.
Compliance with ER	Yes
Verified compliance with standards	While several standards have been identified and followed (details in D3.1, D3.2 and current document), verifying the compliance is not considered a primary goal of the project
Post-production surveillance	Out of project’s scope as this concerns activities after the project end

As the above table clearly depicts, it is safe to conclude that major preparatory activities for this step of the CE marking process have been conducted.

5. *Draw up and keep available the required technical documentation.*

While a big part of the needed technical documentation can be considered done, this is an on-going process which would go on during a future product's lifecycle.

6. *Affix the CE marking and draw up the EU Declaration of Conformity.*

This step is considered out of the project's scope.

As a conclusion, regarding a possible future product development pathway, the WELCOME project's consortium has successfully completed the necessary preparatory steps for a successful CE marking process of the software system, given the project's scope and budget limits.

5 Conclusions

This document, D3.3, has clarified some design issues as requested from the WELCOME project's reviewing process. Furthermore, in this document we described the rationale of the followed design process and the standards on which the design process is based. More specifically, we focused on how the followed process would facilitate a possible future product development pathway and we explicitly described the preparatory steps taken for a possible future CE marking process, even if this is considered out of WELCOME project's scope. The document presents through detailed diagrams the identification of clinical workflows, one per WELCOME pilot site, along with the correspondence of these workflows to the Business Processes defined for WELCOME system. The user privileges per role and application are presented in detail as per application tables and the distinction of data access between sites is further clarified. Also the pseudoanonymisation procedures during registration and data access are presented through clear and easy to follow sequence diagrams. The document presents the strategy regarding the WELCOME data model maintenance and further clarifies how the DSS complex rules were developed. Finally, the consortium provides details regarding the updated risk management policy towards application of the ISO 14971 standard.

Bibliography

1. Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD): Global Strategy for the Diagnosis, Management and Prevention of COPD, 2017 Report (found online at: www.goldcopd.org)
2. Amir Qaseem, MD, PhD, MHA; Timothy J. Wilt, MD, MPH; Steven E. Weinberger, MD; Nicola A. Hanania, MD, MS; Gerard Criner, MD; Thys van der Molen, PhD; Darcy D. Marciniuk, MD; Tom Denberg, MD, PhD; Holger Schunemann, MD, PhD, MSc; Wisia Wedzicha, PhD; Roderick MacDonald, MS; and Paul Shekelle, MD, PhD, for the American College of Physicians, the American College of Chest Physicians, the American Thoracic Society, and the European Respiratory Society. Diagnosis and Management of Stable Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease: A Clinical practice Guideline Update from the American College of Physicians, American College of Chest Physicians, American Thoracic Society, and European Respiratory Society. *Ann Intern Med.* 2011;155:179-191.
3. A Corlateanu, S Covantev, A Mathioudakis, V Botnaru, N Siafakas. Prevalence and Burden of comorbidities in Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease. *Respiratory Investigation* 54(2016):387-396.
4. Aaron SD, Donaldson GC, Whitmore GA, et al. Time course and pattern of COPD exacerbation onset. *Thorax* 2012; 67: 238–243.
5. Vestbo J, Hurd SS, Agusti AG, et al. Global strategy for the diagnosis, management and prevention of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2013; 187: 347–365.
6. Leidy N, Murray L. Patient-reported outcome (PRO) measures for clinical trials of COPD: the EXACT and E-RS. *COPD* 2013; 10: 393–398.
7. Casanova C, Aguirre-Jaime A, de Torres JP, et al. Longitudinal assessment in COPD patients: multidimensional variability and outcomes. *Eur Respir J* 2014; 43: 745–753.
8. Beredimas N., Kilintzis V., Chouvarda I. and Maglaveras N. “A Reusable Ontology for Primitive and Complex HL7 FHIR Data Types”. *Proceedings of 37th IEEE EMBC*, pp. 2547-2550, 2015.
9. The WELCOME consortium, Deliverable 1.1: “D1.1 Quality Management Plan”, 31/01/2014
10. International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), “IEC 62304:2006(en) Medical device software — Software life cycle processes”. <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iec:62304:ed-1:v1:en>
11. International Standards Organization, “ISO 14971 (Medical devices — Application of risk management to medical devices”, http://www.iso.org/iso/catalogue_detail?csnumber=38193
12. Judy A., *Joint application design: the group session approach to system design*, ISBN:0-13-508235-8
13. Erder M, Pureur P. *Continuous Architecture: Sustainable Architecture in an Agile and Cloud-centric World*. Morgan Kaufmann; 2015 Oct 21.

14. Shaw M, DeLine R, Klein DV, Ross TL, Young DM, Zelesnik G. Abstractions for software architecture and tools to support them. IEEE Transactions on software engineering. 1995 Apr;21(4):314-35.
15. The WELCOME consortium, Deliverable 3.1: “D3.1 Initial System Design, Progress on WP3: Complete system design”, 14/11/2014
16. The WELCOME consortium, Deliverable 3.2: “D3.2 Complete System Design, Progress on WP3: Complete system design”, 06/11/2015
17. The WELCOME consortium, Deliverable 5.1: “First prototype of WELCOME Cloud Software”, 06/11/2015

Abbreviations

- CRUD: Create-Retrieve-Update-Delete
- DSS: Decision Support System
- EEA: European Economic Area
- EU: European Union
- FES: Feature Extraction Server
- ICT: Information and Computing Technologies
- IEC: International Electrotechnical Commission
- ISO: International Standards Organization
- JAD: Joint Application Design
- JRD: Joint Requirements Development
- WP: Work Package

Appendix A. Case Studies

Case Study No. 3 Mrs GK (UK team)

Name/ID: Mrs GK

Age: 69

Date: 20/11/13

Venue: 'Acute' home visit

Symptoms/ History of present complaints	Unable to walk upstairs to her second-floor flat without having to rest twice. Feeling dizzy and faint. Increasingly "heavy chest".
Exacerbations (since last seen)	One infective COPD exacerbation in February 2013. Treated with IV co-amoxiclav, clarithromycin and corticosteroids.
Medical History/ Comorbidities	COPD diagnosed in 1997 CHF AF T2DM Hypertension
Social History	Lives with her son-in-law and his family who are main carers. Ex-smoker (gave up in 1992). Alcohol: Nil.
Smoking History Smoking pack years	25 pack years
Allergies	Ramipril (dry cough), metformin (intolerable GI adverse effects)
Medication	Furosemide 80 mg OM, 40 mg afternoon Candesartan 16 mg OM Carvedilol 6.25 mg BD Digoxin 125 micrograms OM Warfarin 5 mg OD (4 mg on Sundays), INR (two weeks ago): 2.7 Gliclazide MR 30 mg tablets 60 mg OM Sitagliptin 100 mg OM Amlodipine 10 mg OM

Respiratory specific medication	Seretide 500 Accuhaler one puff BD Salbutamol Evohaler 100 micrograms one-two puffs PRN (up to QDS)			
BiPap/CPAP?	N/A			
LTOT?				
On Examination	Pronounced right-sided 3 rd heart sound, worsening pulmonary oedema, bilateral peripheral pitting oedema.			
Investigation	Date/time: 21/02/13 (clinic) (In stable state/baseline)	Date/time: 19/11/13	Date/time: 20/11/13	Date/time:
SpO₂	98%	95%	95%	
(In room air or oxygen)	Room air	Room air	Room air	
Oxygen flow rate/ Venturi % mask	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Pulse (regular?)	86/min (AF)	99/min	125/min	
Blood pressure	124/85 mmHg	110/73 mmHg	98/70 mmHg	
Respirations	13/min	17/min	21/min	
Temperature:	36.5	36.9	36.8	
Height	151 cm			
Weight	68 kg	71 kg	72 kg	
BMI	30 kg/m ²			
LV Function	LVEF 56%			
FEV1	53% predicted			
FVC				
FEV1/FVC ratio	0.6			
COPD Severity	Stage 2 - Moderate			

ABG/CBG taken?	No			
pH	N/A			
pCO₂	N/A			
pO₂	N/A			
HCO₃	N/A			
BE	N/A			
SaO₂	N/A			
Blood sugars	Random BG 7.4 mmol/L	8.9 mmol/L	9.3 mmol/L	
HBA1C	N/A			
EIT(Abnormal/Normal/Unknown)				
Ankle oedema	Mild	Moderate pitting	Moderate pitting	
Summary	Mrs GK appears to be experiencing a deterioration in the control of her CHF symptoms displayed as central and peripheral fluid retention with an increase in weight compared to her “dry” baseline weight. This is accompanied by mild hypotension, tachycardia and tachypnoea – likely all secondary to CHF decompensation.			
Management Plan	Self-management advice provided: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stop taking amlodipine until further review (hypotension and peripheral oedema) • Skip one dose of candesartan – re-check blood pressure in 24 hours and ask for a review • Increase the dose of furosemide to 80 mg BD • May use salbutamol Evohaler regularly up to QDS for the next 24-48 hours, however return to PRN use should the pulse increase further or if experiencing palpitations. 			
Follow Up (including any referrals)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor the patient carefully over the next 24 hours. If further deterioration in symptoms and/or fluid retention, consider arranging an emergency home visit or hospital referral. • Bring the INR appointment date forward considering the worsening of patient’s condition which may affect the INR control. • Request a digoxin level at the next GP appointment. • Bring the CHF specialist appointment date forward if no improvement over the next 24-48 hours. 			

Case scenario 2 description (Greek team)

- Vital signs gradually deteriorating during the last 8 hours

- RR= 18 to 21/min
- HR= 85 to 101/min
- SpO₂= 95% (baseline=96%)
- ECG: sinus tachycardia
- Chest sounds: slight prolongation of exhalation time, detection of productive cough
- Temperature= 37,3°C

Initial System Response

- EIT: No difference from baseline
- System sends SMS and email to patient and carer to advice for continuous monitoring through the vest
- Advice to patient to take rescue inhaler therapy (extra salbutamol puffs)
- Prompt for input on dyspnea/ sputum description but patient ignores it
- Informal carer is informed for potential onset of acute exacerbation

Day 2 Signal Reception

- Average RR= 25/min
- HR= 103/min
- SpO₂= 90% (baseline=96%)
- ECG: sinus tachycardia
- Chest sounds: slight prolongation of exhalation time, detection of productive cough, plus crackles in the basal parts of lungs unilaterally
- Temperature= 37,8°C
- EIT: Marked limitation to absence of airflow to the basal parts of lungs (possible pleural effusion)
- Borg dyspnea scale= 8
- Arterial pressure= 155/94mmHg
- Weight= 2 Kg more than 2 days ago
- Reports increased sputum production
- Reported sputum colour = yellow

Day 2 System Response

- System informs pulmonologist and cardiologist about the progress of the symptoms
- MDs decide to activate the prompt for visit to the emergency

- System prompts patient to increase diuretics dosage (40 extra mg of furosemide)
- Advice to patient to visit the emergency department
- Simultaneous information to informal carer
- System annotates obtained data as a new acute exacerbation

Appendix B. WELCOME Application screenshots

A screenshot of the "New Patient" registration form. The form is titled "New Patient" in an orange header bar with a close button (X). It contains several input fields: "First Name *" and "Last Name *" (text boxes), "Gender *" (dropdown menu), "Date of Birth *" (text box with a calendar icon), "Address *" (text box), "Telephone Number *" and "Cellphone Number *" (text boxes), "Login Name *" and "Password *" (text boxes), and "Email *" (text box). Below the email field is an "Upload Photo" section with a "Choose File" button and the text "Upload Jpg, Png, Gif Files". At the bottom right, there is an orange "Add" button.

Figure 25: New patient registration form

Figure 26: Patient container

Figure 27: Equipment container

New Equipment
✕

Serial Number *

Status *

Available
▾

Type *

Glucose meter
▾

Add

Figure 28: New Equipment registration dialog

Patient

Find Patient +

Patient's name

Previous
1
Next

John Doe

41 Years old
10 Jan 1975

Technical Alert

Assigned Doctors: Gregory House

Assigned equipment: Vest, Spirometer

Assigned Carer: -

Dimitrios karamitros

54 Years old
05 Aug 1962

Technical Alert

Assigned Doctors: Gregory House

Assigned equipment: -

Assigned Carer: -

Andreas Raptopoulos

48 Years old
23 Oct 1968

Technical Alert

Assigned Doctors: Gregory House

Assigned equipment: -

Assigned Carer: -

Kostas Anamourloglou

44 Years old
11 Jun 1972

Technical Alert

Assigned Doctors: -

Assigned equipment: -

Assigned Carer: -

Odysseas Bournas

41 Years old
07 Jan 1975

Technical Alert

Assigned Doctors: John Chang

Assigned equipment: Vest^{SN:SN-VEST-11235}

Assigned Carer: -

Equipment

Find Equipment +

Equipment, Patient's Name

Previous
1
Next

Assigned

Previous
1
Next

Vest SN:SN-VEST-11234

Assigned to Patient: John Doe

Spirometer SN:SN-SPIR-11234

Assigned to Patient: John Doe

Unassigned

Previous
1
Next

Vest SN:SN-VEST-11235

Spirometer SN:SN-SPIR-11235

Figure 29: Device assignment to patient

Figure 30: HCP application Calendar module

The "New Appointment" dialog form contains the following fields and controls:

- Patient Name ***: A dropdown menu.
- Appointment Status ***: A dropdown menu.
- Appointment emergency type ***: A dropdown menu.
- Appointment Start Time ***: A time selection control with a dropdown for the hour, a colon separator, a dropdown for the minutes, and a dropdown for AM/PM. The current selection is 05:54 PM.
- Appointment End Time ***: A time selection control with a dropdown for the hour, a colon separator, a dropdown for the minutes, and a dropdown for AM/PM. The current selection is 05:54 PM.
- Appointment Comments**: A text input field.
- Buttons**: "Cancel" and "Create" buttons at the bottom right.

Figure 31: New appointment dialog

Figure 32: Patient application, Diary Module

Figure 33: HCP application, Medical history module

Figure 34: Data Collection application, vest recording screen progress

Figure 35: External devices measurement screen

Figure 36: Patient/Carer application, questionnaire module

Figure 37: Patient/Carer application Diary module

Figure 38: Patient application History module, tabular form

Figure 39: Patient application History module, graph form

John Doe
41 Years old (1975-01-10)
[Contact information](#)
✉ johndow@kingston.co.uk
☎ 1111
📱 22222
[Appointments](#)
Next: *N/A*

- History
- Vital signs
- Notifications
- Questionnaires
- Medication
- Messages**

Recent Messages

How are you feeling today?
You •

I have some troubles today, yes
Doe John •

Are you having any breathing problems?
You •

Enter Message SEND SEND

Figure 40: HCP application Messaging module

Figure 41: HCP application, Measurement module and selection of measurement

Date	Type	View
01/25/2016 , 11:55AM	EDF file	
01/25/2016 , 10:51AM	EDF file	
02/03/2016 , 4:56PM	EDF file	
01/25/2016 , 10:38AM	EDF file	
01/25/2016 , 10:46AM	EDF file	
03/09/2016 , 1:36PM	EDF file	
01/25/2016 , 12:00PM	EDF file	
03/09/2016 , 2:17PM	EDF file	
03/09/2016 , 3:12PM	EDF file	

Figure 42: HCP application, Activity measurement presentation

My Patients
John Doe ✕

John Doe
41 Years old (1975-01-10)

Contact information
✉ johndow@kingston.co.uk
☎ 1111
📠 22222

Appointments
Next: N/A

History

Vital signs

Notifications

Questionnaires

Medication

🖨️ 📄
Notification - Alerts

DSS Alerts

02/04/2016 , 5:45PM	Patient with SpO2 lower than 95%
03/04/2016 , 6:08PM	Patient with SpO2 lower than 95%
02/09/2016 , 1:15AM	Patient with SpO2 lower than 95%
03/03/2016 , 4:59PM	Patient with SpO2 lower than 95%
03/02/2016 , 6:47PM	Patient with SpO2 lower than 95%
01/25/2016 , 4:23AM	Patient with ECG indicating Atrial Fibrillation or Tachycardia, SpO2 lower than 95% , severe dyspnea, increased sputum production and Percentage Predicted FEV1 low
01/25/2016 , 4:50AM	Patient with ECG indicating Atrial Fibrillation or Tachycardia, SpO2 lower than 95% , severe dyspnea, increased sputum production and Percentage Predicted FEV1 low
03/08/2016 , 5:58PM	Patient with SpO2 lower than 95%

Figure 43: HCP application, DSS alerts and notifications

Appendix C. Risk Management File

The provided Risk Management File is maintained as independent file depicting the overall WELCOME project's risk management policy and the identified risks. For practical reasons, its content is provided as an additional document of the current deliverable (part B).